

UNRAVELING THE DIVERSITY OF *Atractus* (SERPENTES: DIPSADIDAE) IN THE VENEZUELAN ANDES

DESENTRAÑANDO LA DIVERSIDAD DE *Atractus* (SERPENTES: DIPSADIDAE) EN LOS ANDES VENEZOLANOS

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ABSTRACT

Today among the recognized species of *Atractus* in Venezuela, the nominal taxa *A. ochrosetrus* Esqueda & La Marca, 2005 and *A. mijaresi* Esqueda & La Marca, 2005, were recently considered a junior synonym of *A. ventrimaculatus* Boulenger, 1905 and *A. pamplonensis* Amaral, 1937, respectively. However, based on new morphological (coloration pattern, scalation, dentition, hemipenes and morphometrics), phylogenetic (topology using Maximum Likelihood + Bayesian Inference and genetic distance) and geographic (ecological niche modeling) evidence, *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. mijaresi*, both endemic species of the cordillera de Mérida, are revalidated and redescribed. The first is restricted to a series of mountain ranges southwest of the Chama River basin, between the states of Mérida and Táchira; while *A. mijaresi* occurs between Mucurubá and Capaz east of the Chama River basin, Mérida state. *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. ventrimaculatus* closely related species diverged in the Late Miocene 6.67 Myr ago (95 % HPD = 4.4-9.02), coinciding with the uplift of the northern Andes between 8-5 Myr. While *A. mijaresi* would be related to *Atractus* sp. yet to be described and that its diversification occurred during the end of the Pliocene and the beginning of the Pleistocene 2.85 Myr ago (95 % HPD = 0.87-5.21). Finally, we record the second specimen from Betania, Táchira state, which we provisionally designate as *Atractus* aff. *pamplonensis*. According to the IUCN, *A. ochrosetrus*, *A. ventrimaculatus* and *A. mijaresi* should be included in the Vulnerable category according to criteria B2 (i,ii,iii,iv)

KEY WORDS: Systematics, taxonomic status, sleepyhead snakes, cordillera de Mérida.

RESUMEN

Hoy en día, entre las especies reconocidas de *Atractus* en Venezuela, los taxones nominales *A. ochrosetrus* (Esqueda & La Marca, 2005) y *A. mijaresi* (Esqueda & La Marca, 2005) fueron considerados recientemente sinónimos menores de *A. ventrimaculatus* (Boulenger, 1905) y *A. pamplonensis* (Amaral, 1937), respectivamente. Sin embargo, con base en nueva evidencia morfológica (patrón de coloración, escamación, dentición, hemipenes y morfometría), filogenética (topología mediante Máxima Verosimilitud + Inferencia Bayesiana y distancia genética) y geográfica (modelado de nicho ecológico), se revalidan y describen *A. ochrosetrus* y *A. mijaresi*, ambas especies endémicas de la cordillera de Mérida. La primera se restringe a una serie de montañas al suroeste de la cuenca del río Chama, entre los estados Mérida y Táchira; mientras *A. mijaresi* se encuentra entre Mucurubá y Capaz al este de la cuenca del río Chama, estado Mérida. *A. ochrosetrus* y *A. ventrimaculatus*, especies estrechamente relacionadas, divergieron en el Mioceno tardío hace 6,67 Myr (95 % HPD = 4,4-9,02), coincidiendo con el levantamiento de los Andes del norte entre 8-5 Myr; en cambio *A. mijaresi* estaría relacionada con *A. xaxi* y su divergencia ocurrió durante el final del Plioceno y el comienzo del Pleistoceno hace 2,85 Myr (95 % HPD = 0,87-5,21). Finalmente, registramos el segundo espécimen de Betania, estado Táchira, al que designamos provisionalmente como *Atractus* aff. *pamplonensis*. Según la UICN, *A. ochrosetrus*, *A. ventrimaculatus* y *A. mijaresi* deben incluirse en la categoría Vulnerable según los criterios B2 (i,ii,iii,iv).

PALABRAS CLAVE: Sistemática, estatus taxonómico, serpientes dormilonas, cordillera de Mérida.

INTRODUCTION

If, as suggested by Zaher *et al.* (2019), dipsadine snakes originated in the Old World and later dispersed to South America, they now exhibit a remarkable ecological and phenotypic diversity as a

result of adaptive radiation, with fossorial snakes clearly differentiating themselves from other groups (Pandelis *et al.* 2023). Considering that dipsadine diversity reaches at least ~806 species (Zaher *et al.* 2019), it is notable, from both evolutionary and ecological perspectives, that the ground or

sleepyhead snakes of the genus *Atractus* Wagler, 1828 represent 18.6 % of all known dipsadines (Uetz *et al.* 2024), clearly establishing themselves as the dominant group in mid- to high-mountain environments across northern South America. In Venezuela, *Atractus* constitutes the most diverse dipsadine genus, with 30 recognized species (Rivas *et al.* 2012, Natera-Mumaw *et al.* 2015).

Recently, some species of the genus were revised by Passos *et al.* (2024) for northern South America (Colombia and Venezuela), with the recognition of five new species for Colombia and the synonymization of five species for Venezuela. Although their article represents progress in understanding these snakes, several of their criteria -such as the adequacy and comparability of data- are dubious, erroneous, incoherent, altered, hidden, and intentionally arranged to create a complex and overlapping scenario that would justify their non-taxonomic recognition. Nevertheless, their cautious and convenient discussion suggests that a future phylogenetic hypothesis or additional evidence could alter these taxonomic decisions. Although the taxonomy and systematics of this group have advanced significantly in recent decades (e.g., an increase in described diversity; Uetz *et al.* 2024), the incorporation of molecular data has revealed that the group's diversity may be even greater, and that in many cases, multiple lines of evidence are required for proper species recognition (Arteaga *et al.* 2017, 2022, Melo-Sampaio *et al.* 2019, 2021, Passos *et al.* 2022).

In their monograph, Passos *et al.* (2024) overlooked, evaded, or confused fundamental criteria for understanding species formation and differentiation. From John Ray's systematic concept (Ray 1686), through the theory of evolution (Darwin 1859, Darwin & Wallace 1859), to current advances in molecular biology, the concept of species has evolved shifting from a purely morphological framework, now regarded as a weak criterion for delimiting true species, toward a more integrative and dynamic perspective (Wiens & Servedio 2000). Speciation, understood as a complex and discrete process (Rabosky *et al.* 2013), does not always produce clear boundaries between species (Walker *et al.* 2024), leading to the acceptance that species may represent temporary segments of stabilizing lineages. If a lineage is defined as a sequence of ancestor-descendant populations or metapopulations (e.g., unified species concept; de Queiroz 2007), then species can be considered, synergistically, as segments of that lineage. Although phenotypic discontinuities

between organismal groups may reflect only selective advantages of certain trait combinations, in the context of speciation, species represent temporary fragments of stabilized lineages (Dupré 2024).

Within this framework, polymorphism - particularly in coloration- serves as an excellent model for studying ecological and evolutionary processes, as different morphologies, maintained by genetic mechanisms, can reflect adaptations to local selective pressures. Polymorphism is defined as the occurrence of two or more clearly distinct, genetically determined morphs or forms at the intrapopulation level, maintained through interbreeding (Forsman 2016, McLean & Stuart-Fox 2016, White & Kemp 2016), with relatively high frequencies (>1%). Geographic variants that imply isolation leading to allopatric speciation are excluded; polymorphisms occur strictly within panmictic populations, and rare variations or mutations are not considered polymorphisms. It is important to distinguish between polymorphism with at least two known morphs (dichromatism) and those involving multiple morphs, which are more common in nature (polychromatism). Notably, distinct color morphs are not necessarily genetically determined they may be induced by environmental cues or depend on the organism's developmental stage (polyphenisms; Mayr 1963, Pfenning & McGee 2010). Polymorphisms are also frequently associated with species radiations, in which multiple closely related species exhibit similar intraspecific morphs (Gray & McKinnon 2007, Hugall & Stuart-Fox 2012, Jamie & Meier 2020, Enbody *et al.* 2021).

Building on the speciation polymorphism framework, phenomena such as melanism -subject to natural and sexual selection- can influence selection and frequency patterns (Prince 2003), potentially leading to adaptive responses that accumulate significant genetic differences and trigger speciation events. This pattern is evident, for instance, in *Atractus* species from montane environments, where pigmentation differences appear associated with geographic isolation and potential recent diversification events that have yet to be fully explored.

The coadaptation hypothesis suggests a correlation among multiple traits within a species - such as morphology (e.g., body shape, coloration), thermoregulatory behavior, and thermal performance- allowing them to evolve together (Huey & Bennett 1987, Bauwens *et al.* 1995, Angilletta *et al.* 2002). Thus, darker coloration may

promote greater heat absorption and confer advantages in colder climates (mid- to high-mountain zones, Bogert's rule; Bogert 1949, Clusella-Trullas *et al.* 2007), though it can also occur in lowland taxa (Gloger's rule; Gloger 1833, Rensch 1929). Although this suggests potential adaptive responses, little is known about the underlying mechanisms regulating these relationships and how frequent they are within populations, particularly regarding their taxonomic significance and how population-level patterns respond to local selective pressures, resulting in distinctive traits and genetic adaptations (Mimura *et al.* 2017). Furthermore, it seems plausible that the establishment of genetically based geographic variation (genetic accommodation; West-Eberhard 2003) and species differences in melanin patterns are favored by environmental effects on melanin intensity and pattern, as observed between *A. taphorni* vs. *A. emigdioi* and *A. ventrimaculatus* vs. *A. ochrosetrus* -closely related species occurring allopatrically in mid- to high-elevation environments of the cordillera de Mérida (Esqueda *et al.* 2025b,c).

Herein, we re-evaluate and revalidate the taxonomy of *A. ochrosetrus* vs. *A. ventrimaculatus* and *A. mijaresi* vs. *A. pamplonensis* by integrating morphological and molecular data an approach not previously applied. All are endemic species of the cordillera de Mérida, except *A. pamplonensis*, whose presence in Venezuela is based on a single specimen identified by Schargel & García-Pérez (2002), notably not evaluated by Passos *et al.* (2024). We formally include the description of a second specimen from the same locality, defined here as *Atractus* aff. *pamplonensis*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

DNA extraction, amplification and sequencing

DNA was extracted from intercostal muscles, liver, and heart tissues of specimens collected by Luis Felipe Esqueda (LFE) and preserved in 95 % ethanol. Specimens were later transferred to 75 % ethanol and deposited in the Zoology Museum of the University of Concepción, Chile (MZUC). Additional tissues, preserved using the same protocol, were provided from sources like MHNLS, Venezuela. Extractions and amplifications followed the Wizard® SV Genomic DNA Purification System protocol (PROMEGA, USA) at the Herpetozoa laboratory, University of Concepción. Two mitochondrial genes (Cytb and ND4) and two nuclear genes (NT3 and RAG-1) were amplified

using primers and PCR conditions detailed in Supp._1_1, DNA quality was assessed on 1.5 % agarose gels stained with SYBR® Vitrogen. Sequencing was performed by MACROGEN (Korea), and chromatograms were verified using BioEdit 7.0.9.0 (Hall 1999). Open reading frames were checked in Mega v.11 (Tamura *et al.* 2021). Heterozygous nuclear DNA sequences were identified visually for double peaks in chromatograms, and individual alleles were reconstructed using DnaSP v.6.12 (Librado & Rozas 2009) with two independent runs. Alignments showed no gaps in mitochondrial sequences, and sequences for other species were sourced from GenBank (Supp._1_2), ensuring amplified loci were from single voucher specimens to avoid “terminal chimeras”.

Phylogenetic analyses

The new sequences generated in this study were combined with sequences downloaded from GenBank. Additionally, 20 specimens representing to 18 species were used as outgroups (highlighted in yellow, Supp._1_2). Five gene fragments were obtained, corresponding to three mitochondrial amplicons, long 16S ribosomal RNA (525 bp); cytochrome b (897 bp); and NADH dehydrogenase ND4 subunit IV (713 bp) and two nuclear amplicons, neurotrophin-3 gene NT3 (516 bp); recombination activator RAG-1 (879 bp). Substitution saturation of each locus was assessed using the software DAMBE v.5 (Xia 2013). We also assessed congruence among gene phylogenies by running individual gene tree analyses and calculating gene (gCF) and site (sCF) concordance factors in IQtree v.2 (Nguyen *et al.* 2015).

The authenticity of the obtained sequences and the homology of the specific mtDNA and nuDNA markers were evaluated with a BLAST search in the NCBI genetic database (<http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>). The consensus sequences for each locus were aligned using MAFFT (Kato & Standley 2013) contained in Jalview v. 2.11.1.4 (Waterhouse *et al.* 2009), L.INS-i option with the following parameters: gap: 1.53 and gap: 0.123, BLOSUM62 and 200PAM/k=2 (except region 16S aligned with the E.INS-i option). Only 16S mtDNA alignments that exhibit nucleotide positions with high entropy and may have misaligned or incongruent regions were refined with the BMGE software: a BLOSUM62 matrix, a minimum block size of 20, a maximum entropy threshold of 0.5, and a rate limit gap of 0.65 (Criscuolo & Gribaldo 2010), available on the web

service <https://ngphylogeny.fr/> (Lemoine *et al.* 2019). Finally, the concatenation of all alignments was done with Mesquite v3.6 (Maddison & Maddison 2021). Given the use of coding genes, all nucleotide sequences were translated into amino acids to evaluate the reading frame and ensure the absence of premature stop codons or other nonsense mutations (Triant & Dewoody 2007).

Here, we used maximum likelihood (ML) analysis to obtain the optimal tree topology of the concatenated data set. The best partition and substitution models were automatically selected using ModelFinder (Kalyaanamoorthy *et al.* 2017) and then implemented in IQ-TREE v.2 software (Nguyen *et al.* 2015) under the Bayesian information criterion (BIC). The best ML tree was selected from 10,000 iterations and the confidence of the branches of the best ML tree was evaluated with the ultrafast bootstrap method using 10,000 bootstrap pseudoreplicates (Minh *et al.* 2013). Posteriorly, we ran 20 individual runs to avoid possible local optima using the following configuration: `Iqtree2 -s myfile -m TESTMERGE -ninit 200 -nstop 1000 -pers 0.2 -ntop 100 -nbest 20 -rcluster 30 -alrt 1000 -bb 10,000`. Previously we performed runs for each locus on the web-server Iqtree (<http://iqtree.cibiv.univie.ac.at/>, Trifinopoulos *et al.* 2016), where branch support was calculated using the ultrafast bootstrap approximation (UFBS) (Minh *et al.* 2013) and the Shimodaira-Hasegawa approximate likelihood ratio test (SH-aLRT) (Anisimova *et al.* 2011), with 1,000 replicas. The consensus tree was visualized in FigTree (Rambaut 2014). Nodes with bootstrap values ≥ 70 were considered strongly supported and those nodes with 95 % were considered highly supported.

Divergence time estimation and calibration points

We estimated divergence times of sleepyhead snakes of the genus *Atractus* using the Bayesian framework implemented in the BEAST 2.7.5 software (Bouckaert & Drummond 2017). For all analyses, the matrix was partitioning by genes, coding loci such as Cytb and ND4 treated separately forming non-coding loci like 16S, except nuclear markers NT3, RAG-1 and CMOS, where we applied a linked strategy to avoid overparameterization. Unlike previous analyses with maximum likelihood (ML) and Bayesian inference (BI), where the best partition schemes and molecular evolution models were defined using ModelFinder and Partition Finder in the integrated PhyloSuite platform (Zhang *et al.* 2020). Here, the

BEAST 2.7.5 software implements the “bModelTest “allreversible” option to estimate mutation rates for all genes evaluated. When implemented, bModelTest switches between substitution models during the Metropolis coupled MCMC (MC3), inferring and marginalizing site models, thus averaging the uncertainty about those models (Bouckaert & Drummond 2017), except for partitions that were defined by PartitionFinder because bModelTest does not incorporate substitution models average site over partitions from alignment. While Bayesian relaxed clock methods may produce more correct estimates when using multiple loci (mtDNA + nuDNA) (Battistuzzi *et al.* 2010), it is unclear how using faster-evolving mitochondrial genes (animals) may influence dating by divergence in relation to the use of nuclear loci that have a slower rate of evolution (Zheng *et al.* 2011). Here, the likelihood ratio test (LRT) implemented in Mega v.11 software (Kumar *et al.* 2018) rejected strict clock evolution models, favoring the lognormal relaxed clock model for all partitions. Although the classic uncorrelated relaxed clock (Drummond *et al.* 2006) works well when rates and branch lengths are not highly correlated, on the contrary, it is poor, so here we will use the “optimized relaxed clock” model according to Douglas *et al.* (2021) which works well in both scenarios. On the other hand, we will apply a birth-death speciation model (Kendall 1948) as opposed to the Yule model (Yule 1925), since this assumes zero extinction rates and it is commonly known that extinction is extremely significant in the diversification of species (Sarver *et al.* 2019). Other antecedents were set to their default values, except the birth rate, which had an exponential distribution (lower 0.1 and upper 10).

Phylogenetic analyses often involve data sets comprising sequences from multiple loci. A common practice is to partition the data set, for example, by gene or by codon position, and assign separate substitution models to subsets of the data (Yang & Kumar 1996). In molecular clock analyses, the simplest approach is to apply a single model of rate variation between lineages to the entire sequence alignment. However, this approach does not account for heterogeneity between genes, which may have evolved under very different conditions. For instance, multilocus data sets may include combinations of markers from mitochondrial, chloroplast, and nuclear genomes. An ideal scenario for calibrating phylogenetic trees is when they are obtained from well-dated fossils; however, the incomplete or imperfect nature of the fossil record often only provides evidence of the minimum age of

a clade, potentially leading to overestimation divergence time (Lukoschek *et al.* 2012). In fact, fossils rarely represent specific nodes but rather points along a branch (Lee 1999, Conroy & van Tuinen 2003).

On the other hand, multiple underlying factors can contribute to inaccurately calibrated clocks (e.g., patterns of evolution, saturation, and/or combinations of genes that evolve more rapidly vs. others that evolve more slowly). In snakes, the Caenophidia group contains the greatest diversity of extant snakes (> 2500 spp., Uetz *et al.* 2024) and includes acrochordids, xenodermids and all colubriforms (Pyron *et al.* 2013), a group with a controversial fossil record (Head 2015, Head *et al.* 2016). Considering the countless setbacks that persist in obtaining ultrametric trees (Lukoschek *et al.* 2012), there is greater consensus on using multiple independent calibrations of fossils (Ho & Phillips 2009). In our case, the calibration points of the nodes were defined based on the available fossil record (one corresponding to Colubridae and four positioned in the external groups), using ages and interpretations of fossils similar to those described in Zaher *et al.* (2018, 2019) and García-Sotelo *et al.* (2021) (Supp._1_3). We use Metropolis coupled MCMC (MC3, Atchadé *et al.* 2011, Maturana-Russel *et al.* 2018, Müller and Bouckaert 2019), with a temperature of 0.03 and four chains, established in three independent runs of 50 million generations, saving the parameters and trees every 10,000 generations (10,000 trees/runs). The convergence of the runs, effective sample size (ESS) values, and optimal burn-up values were verified using Tracer v1.7 (Rambaut *et al.* 2022). Combining the runs was done with LogCombiner v2.7.5 (Drummond *et al.* 2012). After performing a 10 % burning, the maximum credible tree was obtained by using TreeAnnotator 2.7.5 (Rambaut & Drummond 2016) implemented on the CIPRES Science Gateway online platform (<https://www.phylo.org/>) (Miller *et al.* 2010).

Finally, we also calculated the uncorrected genetic distance (p-distance) using MEGA v.11.0 (Kumar *et al.* 2018) for mitochondrial CYTb and ND4, respectively.

Ecological niche modeling

To understand the distribution and habitat in the biogeographic context, we generated species distribution models (SDM) to predict and compare the potential geographic ranges of *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. ventrimaculatus* using correctly identified

records (including material MZUC museum by LFE). Therefore, those records that could be downloaded from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF, <http://www.gbif.org>) and iDigBio (www.idigbio.org) databases that we could not verify were discarded, being in total 49 records/specimens between both taxa verified (Supp._1_4).

Input data (records and environmental variables)

Each record's coordinates were obtained via Google Earth, converted to decimal degrees, and saved in CSV format. Environmental predictors included 20 bioclimatic variables representing the current scenario (1970-2000) from WorldClim v.2.1 (Fick & Hijmans 2017), with a spatial resolution of ~5 km (2.5 arc-minutes). These variables encompassed 19 climate-related factors (temperature and precipitation) and elevation as a topographic variable. Additional environmental layers were sourced from EarthEnv (<http://www.earthenv.org>), including continuous topographic variables with ~5 km resolution (Amatulli *et al.* 2018). After modeling in MaxEnt, the vegetation map of Venezuela by Huber and Oliveira-Miranda (2010) was used to calculate the surface area (km²) predicted by the model and to exclude areas inconsistent with the species' ecological preferences. Protected area maps, downloaded as shapefiles from Provita (<https://geoportal.provita.org.ve/>), were also used to determine the overlap between predicted distributions and conservation areas. Environmental layers were processed into raster format using QGIS v.3.28 (QGIS Development Team 2024).

Approach to predictive models (habitat suitability)

Exploring habitat suitability using a unique model (SDMs): given the limited and spatially concentrated occurrence data (Hernandez *et al.* 2006), Our first approach was based on a unique maximum entropy model to predict the distribution range of the species (MaxEnt v.3.4; Phillips *et al.* 2006). This algorithm is highly effective for inferring species suitability from presence-only data, even with small sample sizes, due to its ability to estimate probabilities based on maximum entropy principles (Phillips *et al.* 2006, Elith *et al.* 2011, Warren & Seifert 2011). In the first instances, doubtful information and duplicate records were removed. To reduce collinearity among bioclimatic variables, we performed a Pearson (Pearson 1900) correlation analysis in R (v.4.3) using ENMTools

(Supp_1_5; Warren *et al.* 2021), discarding variables with $r^2 > 0.8$ (Dormann *et al.* 2013), resulting in seven bioclimatic variables in the present scenery (Supp_1_6). In MaxEnt, we disabled Extrapolate and Do clamping to avoid overfitting (Elith *et al.* 2011). Due to fewer than 50 records by species, we used Crossvalidate for stable evaluation, with a convergence limit of 0.00001, default prevalence of 0.65, 10 percentile training presence rules, and a max of 5,000 iterations. We randomly selected 65 % of sites for training and 25 % for testing (Phillips *et al.* 2006). The Jackknife test was used to estimate the contribution and response of each variable (Shcheglovitova & Anderson 2013).

To understand changes in habitat suitability that presumably led to historical isolation or not during restriction to shared refugia, we retrospectively projected current MDS onto Pleistocene and Pliocene climate data available in the PaleoClim database (Brown *et al.* 2018, <http://www.paleoclim.org/>). In this particular, projections were used for the mid-Pliocene warm period, between 3,264-3,025 Myr (Downset *et al.* 2010) and Last Maximum Glacial (LGM, 21 Kya; Karger *et al.* 2017). It should be noted that not all bioclimatic variables are represented in these projections, so we generated SDMs with a subset of variables represented in paleoclimate datasets (BIO_1, BIO_3, BIO_4, BIO_12, BIO_13, BIO_17 and BIO_18) using the same approach as current models and predicted habitat suitability with the predictive function in MaxEnt v.3.4 (Phillips *et al.* 2006).

Evaluation index and visualization

The accuracy of the models either in the single approach was evaluated as follows: (1) single approach: the model outputs were manually checked, and the model with the largest area under the curve (AUC) was selected. AUC values range from 0.5 (random model) to 0.8-0.9 (good fit) and above 0.9 (excellent fit) (Thuiller *et al.* 2003). The logistic output indicates a probabilistic similarity index, with values from 0 to 1, where values closer to 1 represent ideal conditions for the species. While the AUC test is commonly used in species distribution models (e.g., MaxEnt), its validation has been questioned for not accounting for true absences, leading to uncertain models (Peterson & Nakazawa 2008). To avoid biases, additional statistical metrics, including the Z value, were used to assess the significance of the predictions (Manly 2006). The True Skill Statistic (TSS) compares

sensitivity and specificity, providing a robust, prevalence-independent metric, with values close to 1 indicating excellent predictive capacity (Allouche *et al.* 2006). Before running MaxEnt, we optimized the model configuration using the ENMeval library (Muscarella *et al.* 2014; Supp_1_7) in R v.4.3 (R Core Team 2020), selecting the best model based on the Akaike Information Criterion corrected for small sample sizes (AICc). Using selected multipliers and feature types (e.g., linear, quadratic), we compared models based on a threshold-dependent approach and evaluated omissions and significance rates. Models with better predictions showed low omission and performed statistically better than random predictions (Phillips *et al.* 2006). Although we performed 10 replicas to calibrate our present model, only the best-fitted model ultimately ran above the critical values of TSS (> 0.4) and AUC (> 0.7).

The analysis of the niche is carried out separately for each species of *Atractus* using the R ecospat library (Di Cola *et al.* 2017). The ecological space (E-space) is evaluated using an ambient PCA environment (PCA-env hereafter) framework and an ordination approach. Climatic variables transform into three-dimensional spaces defined by their main components. The superposition of niches between *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. ventrimaculatus* was calculated using Schoener's D statistics directly on the ecological niche space and modified Hellinger distances (Schoener 1968, Warren *et al.* 2008). The value of D varies between 0, when the species do not overlap in the ambient space, and 1, when the species compare with in the same ambient space. We evaluate the conservation of niche (alternative = major, is decided, the superposition of niche is more equivalent/similar than random) and niche divergence (alternative = smaller, i.e., niche overlap is less equivalent/similar than random) (Broennimann *et al.* 2012, Di Cola *et al.* 2017). For each hypothesis, 1,000 permutations were made. All these analyses were executed in R v.4.3 (R Core Team 2020).

To account for the actual suitability of the habitat, we used vegetation cover data made by Chacón-Moreno & Moral (2020). Next, we recalculated the resulting output of the models in each, which were filtered in QGIS v.3.28 for values < 0.15 , and the potential distribution was refined in R v.4.3 (R Core Team 2020) using raster, sf, and dplyr libraries by excluding areas with unsuitable vegetation or land use. Finally, we used all available sighting records of the taxon to determine its extent of occurrence (EOO; minimum convex polygon

encompassing all known occurrences, excluding inconsistencies) and area of occupancy (AOO; recount of 2-km² grid cells identified with sighting records or with suitable habitat encircled by grid cells with sighting records within the EOO; IUCN 2022). Comparatively, we use the geospacial conservation evaluation tool to calculate the metrics EOO and AOO, that allow us to evaluate the status of focal species according to IUCN (geocat, <http://geocat.kew.org/>, accessed 8 March, 2025) (Bachman *et al.* 2011). This online tool type open source is an application based on the web of the IUCN red list by laying georeferenced data on the species by Google Maps interface (IUCN 2012).

Sample source

This study includes the review of 292 specimens collected in the field during 2021 north of the Orinoco River, whose scientific hunting permits and access to genetic resources were processed and approved before the Ministerio de Ecosocialismo y Aguas (MINEC-Venezuela) under N° DGBD/2021/0095 to Luis Felipe Esqueda (LFE). Not all the material has been formally deposited in the museum yet (Museum of Zoology of the University of Concepción, Chile, MZUC). Moreover, additional examined material is deposited in the following institutions: Laboratorio de Biogeografía, Universidad de Los Andes, Mérida, Venezuela (ULABG); Museo de Vertebrados de la Universidad de Los Andes, Mérida, Venezuela (CVULA); Museo de la Estación Biológica Rancho Grande, Maracay, Aragua, Venezuela (EBRG); Museo de Ciencias Naturales de Caracas, Venezuela (MCNC); Museo de Historia Natural La Salle, Caracas, Venezuela (MHNLS); British Museum Natural History, London, United Kingdom (BMNH); Museum of Comparative Zoology, Cambridge, USA (MCZ) and American Museum of Natural History, New York, USA (AMNH).

Morphometric and morphological data

Previously, all available information about Venezuelan species were reviewed (Boulenger 1903, Roze 1961, 1966, Lancini 1969, González-Sponga 1971, Barros 2000, Schargel & García-Pérez 2002, Markezich & Barrio-Amorós 2004, Sánchez *et al.* 2004, Esqueda & La Marca 2005, Kok 2006, Myers & Schargel 2006, Esqueda *et al.* 2007, Passos *et al.* 2009b, 2013, Esqueda 2011, Prudente & Passos 2012, Natera-Mumaw *et al.* 2015, Monte-Correa *et al.* 2017, Passos *et al.* 2024) and other related species from Colombia (Pérez-Santos y Moreno 1988, Passos *et al.* 2009a,c,d, 2010, Meneses-

Pelayo *et al.* 2019), Ecuador (Schargel *et al.* 2013, Salazar-Valenzuela *et al.* 2014, Arteaga *et al.* 2017, 2022) and Brazil (Cuhna & Nascimento 1983, Martins & Oliveira 1993, Passos *et al.* 2005, 2010, 2022).

For each specimen of the species evaluated, including candidate species, detailed descriptions of meristic and morphological characters were available, defined in five informative categories: (1) scutellation, encompassing the head and body; (2) measurements of total length and tail, along with certain cephalic scutellation measurements; (3) coloration in life and/or preserved; (4) structure and systematic characteristics of the hemipenis, and (5) cranial osteology, particularly regarding the maxillary bone and teeth. The latter three depends on items the availability of information, although hemipenial and osteological data were included whenever possible.

With respect to scutellation, the terminology for head shields, dorsal, ventral and subcaudal counts for the genus *Atractus* follows that indicated by Dowling (1951), Savage (1960), Hoogmoed (1980), Myers (2003) and Natera-Mumaw *et al.* (2015).

Due to their taxonomic importance in the genus, some characters are defined as follows: rostral scute in dorsal view, there can be defined as three states: condition A, barely visible from above, with the apex of the scale contacting the internasals being narrow, rounded or forming an obtuse angle, below the imaginary straight line between nostrils; apical width is less than the distance between nostrils. Condition B, something visible from above, where the distal portion of the scale exceeds the imaginary line, usually narrow toward its distal portion; apical width less or equal than the distance between nostrils, but does not exceed the internasal suture and (C) distinctly visible, with the scale measured between its supralabial contacts, always forming an obtuse angle and above the imaginary straight line between nostrils; apical width > 0.5 than the distance between nostrils, always greater than or equal to the internasal suture. Additional details, such as the presence or absence of a medial projection, vary from these three conditions of the rostral and are of taxonomic importance. The region that includes the snout has two conditions, weak or strongly compressed, which can be quantitatively verified which can be quantitatively verified if compared with the interocular distance.

Contact between the first supralabial and rostral scute in lateral view; can be short-moderate its

contact, occurs when less than or equal the height of the supralabial and ample contact, it happens when it exceeds half the height of the supralabial. Eye-Loreal contact narrow, when it is less than half of the suture between prefrontal and postnasal and wider; when its width is at least half or more of the width of prefrontal suture and postnasal, so it is similar to its width towards the contact with the postnasal. Eye-Prefrontal contact is narrow, smaller than the prefrontal-postnasal suture and extensive when it is greater than half, equal to or larger than the prefrontal-postnasal suture.

Here, we follow the proposal made by Natera-Mumaw *et al.* (2015) for loreal scale, a short loreal (condition A), occurs when its length is less than HED and always in contact with two supralabials (e.g., *A. elaps*, *A. latifrons*, and *A. steyermarki*, Savage 1960, Passos *et al.* 2013, Almeida *et al.* 2014); moderate loreal (condition B), occur when its length is greater than HED, but ≤ 1.5 times HED, may be in contact with two or three supralabial scales; in addition, there are two conditions, the first occurs when the loreal and supralabial margin that contacts previously are less than the height of loreal measured at the angle between supralabial and another state occurs when ALO is greater than the margin between loreal and anterior supralabial in contact. Finally, elongated loreal (condition C), occurs when its length is greater than 1.5 times HED, frequently in contact with three supralabials, the margin between loreal and anterior supralabial is greater than ALO (e.g., *A. torquatus*, *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. heyeri*; Esqueda 2015, Natera-Mumaw *et al.* 2015). However, exist exceptions where with an elongated loreal, only two supralabials are in contact, just as it happens with *A. emigdioi* González-Sponga, 1971 and *A. multidentatus* Passos, Rivas-Fuenmayor & Barrio-Amorós, 2009 (see also species from Ecuador; Arteaga *et al.* 2017, 2022). In each case mentioned, we can find that the margin between loreal and anterior supralabial can be less or greater than ALO, and relating to condition B, there may be exceptionally individuals with loreal in contact with three supralabial (e.g., *A. ventrimaculatus*, LFE unpublished data). On the other hand, we consider three types of snouts in dorsal view: one short with an FRD equal to or less than 1.5 times END, moderate between 1.5-2 times END, and long greater than 2.5 times END.

Regarding the count of infralabial scales, they are considered infralabial up to the labial commissure, in contact with the last supralabial in lateral view. We do not consider small adjacent scales as infralabial, sometimes there are one or two

in contact with the supralabial when the mouth is closed in lateral view, therefore, it is defined how many infralabials are in contact with the greats. Sublabial scale, has gone unnoticed but is confused in the descriptions, this scale has two states, in contact with each other, it occurs when separating the middle gular from the posterior contact with the genials; some authors in the past have considered it a second pair of genials. In fact, in the genus *Geophis*, many of its species often have this characteristic (Downs 1967).

There are two scales that tend to be conflictive and whose usefulness has not been clearly defined (we have personally observed intraspecific variability), gulars and preventral (s). In the first order of ventral arrangement of the head, genials is arranged along the head, posteriorly begins the gular rows and between sublabials (first gular that contacts with genials). Next, there are several preventral ones, less wide than the ventral ones in the strict sense, in lateral contact with the first dorsal rows behind the parietal ones. The remaining scales of the body, both dorsally and ventrally, have a definition and count that follow what was previously known. Melo-Sampaio & Venegas (2023) when describing a new species from Peru, pointed out the presence of apical pits, an attribute absent in all the other species that we know. Later, it will be necessary for an exhaustive analysis (electron microscopy) to corroborate or not, which makes us assume that it could be more of a conservation artifact. For all measurements and descriptions of cephalic scutellation they are strictly based on the right side of the head but verified on both sides.

Morphometric measurements and meristic counting were carried out through scaled images and using software Image J v.1.54d, as follows: **TL**, total length from snout to the tip of the tail; **TaL**, tail length; **HL**, head length, from tip of snout to end of parietal suture; **HW**, head width measured between labial commissures in dorsal view; **FL**, frontal length; **FW**, frontal width measured from in the anterior portion between the eyes; **PSL**, parietal suture length; **PrSL**, prefrontal suture length; **ISL**, suture length between internasals; **FRD**, distance between frontal and rostral; **ID**, interocular distance; **IND**, internostril distance; **HED**, horizontal eye diameter; **END**, eye-nostril distance; **LOL**, loreal length; **ALO**, height of the loreal measured at the angle between two supralabials; **TEL**, first temporal length; **SupL**, length of the first supralabial in contact with the ocular orbit; **SLG**, suture length between genials; **RoW**, rostral scale width measured between supralabials; **RoDW**, distal

width of the rostral measured between nostrils; **WMB**, width at the middle of the body.

Here, we consider dorsal and ventral coloration in life as the first distinguishing option among *Atractus*, since some details are lost during preservation. The dorsal body pattern is divided into three sections, vertebral, paravertebral, and dorsolateral. Here, we differentiate dots or blotches arranged on the dorsum of the body, where dots occupy less than three dorsal scales, and blotches extend to more than three scales; the presence of a cream border on dots or blotches is called margination. Regarding the longitudinal lines or stripes, these can be narrow (< a dorsal scale) or wide (> a dorsal scale), continuous or discontinuous and arranged in any section of the dorsal region. If we consider the previous arguments, exist three base patterns with variants: one uniform without blotches, dots, or lines-stripes, with 1-3 differentiated dorsal rows (light in preserved and reddish, yellowish, or cream in life); blotched or dotted, where the blotches or dots may or may not be circumscribed, marginalized or not and with one or more lines-stripes an along the body. The ventral surface of the body and tail, consist of three patterns and their variants, the first is considered immaculate, and may sometimes have small scattered dots or blotches but which do not occupy 15 % of the scale surface; blotches or dots disposed horizontally on the scale, giving the impression of one or varies discontinuous lines-stripes, it may be little evident anteriorly and intensifies towards the cloaca; interspersed or irregular blotches, forming blocks that occupy at least 60 % of the scale, sometimes a wide line is observed medially and finally the ventral region is completely stained, less common than the other patterns.

The maxillary bone of one or several specimens was extracted (left sides) and posteriorly cleaned using KOH 3 % by 10 minutes and distilled water for 10 hours. Then scale photos were taken using an Olympus E620 camera fixed to brand stereoscopic magnifying glass. In the remaining specimens examined; after cleaning the maxillary bone of tissue, the arranged teeth or sockets were counted to eliminate the erroneous count.

The extraction and preparation of the hemipenial organs followed the procedures described by Manzani & Abe (1988), modified by Pesantes (1994) and Zaher (1999) for snakes. Passos *et al.* (2016) replaced the KOH indicated in Pesantes (1994) with distilled water. We adopted both procedures, but in a different way, which was a successful way to

achieve organ extension. The most common is that the hemipenes have not been previously partially or totally extracted at the time of conservation of the specimen, being fixed with formaldehyde and/or ethanol, where the first option exists much more rigidity and mostly the tail could have been fixed with little formaldehyde (pers. obs. LFE). Recovering the elasticity of the organ is the most important step, because later on using a burnisher with a spherical tip, the tissue can be moved until its maximum extension is achieved. For this reason, three emersion stations were established, the first with distilled water at 60 °C for 2-3 minutes, the second with 3 % KOH for one minute and the third with distilled water at room temperature for 10-30 minutes. If the time is right, you will be able to see the organ in a transparent amber color, otherwise, do stations 1 and 3 again. Before starting to use the burnisher to extend the tissue, it is advisable to inject glycerin + water into the tissue from the base that connects with the muscle. This procedure guarantees that when the burnisher is introduced, it can move due to lubrication, with retraction movements that allow the extension of the hemipenis to be observed. Once the extension of the hemipenis has been achieved, vaseline or glycerin + water is injected and the base is tied, then it is immersed in a solution of 70 % ethanol and alizarin red or candle color for about 10 minutes, and finally it is stored in an Eppendorf with glycerin. With respect to the calcareous structure's ornamentation, we follow to Uzzell (1973) and Harvey & Embert (2008). Qualitative and quantitative description of hemipenial characters follows Dowling & Savage (1960), Uzzell (1973), Zaher (1999), Myers & Cadle (2003), Schargel & Castoe (2003), Zaher & Prudente (2003), Myers & McDowell (2014) and Passos *et al.* (2016). Although the term "diastema" has been considered in the past for this group of snakes, being a distinctive character (e.g., Passos *et al.* 2009a,c, Passos & Lynch 2010). We will talk about space and/or reduction between the last teeth, following the indicated by Oliveira *et al.* (2023), who recognize that goo-eating dipsadines do not present diastema.

RESULTS

Phylogenetic approach

The final concatenated molecular data set consists of 3535 bp corresponding to three mitochondrial genes (136 sequences in 16S: 525 bp, 130 informative sites, 45 singleton, 350 conserved sites, missing data 0.76-30 %; 97 sequences in Cytb: 897 bp , 425 informative sites, 71 singleton, 401

conserved sites, missing data 0-34 % and 111 sequences in ND4: 713 bp, 363 informative sites, 44 singleton, 323 conserved sites, missing data 0-29 %) and two nuclear genes (79 sequences in NT3: 521 bp, 91 informative sites, 50 singleton, 375 conserved sites, missing data 0-25 % and 63 sequences in RAG-1: 879 bp, 90 informative sites, 95 singleton, 694 sites preserved, missing data 0-18 %). 172 samples/terminals of *Atractus* and 19 samples/terminals as outgroups (Boidae = 2 spp., Viperidae = 4 spp., Colubridae = 5 spp. and Dipsadidae = 8 spp.).

The molecular phylogenetic trees resulting from the ML (Fig. 1) and BI (Fig. 2) analyses are consistent and similar in topology, suggesting that the data provide a robust phylogenetic signal recognized by both methods. However, the node support within *Atractus* was generally < 0.5 in for BI. Differences in support between ML and IB may stem from the way these methods handle uncertainty and evolution models (Alfaro *et al.* 2003, Holder & Lewis 2003, Yang & Rannala 2012). In our study, posterior probability values above 0.95 were considered strongly supported, values between 0.7 and 0.95 was moderately supported, and below 0.7 as weakly supported. The monophyly of *Atractus* was well-supported in the ML analysis, where it was divided into two major lineages (ML and BI).

Our time-calibrated phylogeny recovered estimates the most recent common ancestor (TMRCA) of *Atractus* at 22.54 Myr during the Early Miocene (95 % HDP = 19.08-26.23). **Lineage A**, that included clade constitutes by *A. multicinctus* (Jan, 1865), *A. lasallei* Amaral, 1931 and *A. imperfectus* Myers, 1903. **Lineage B** has a TMRCA of 21.54 Myr (95% HDP = 18.09-24.78) are includes: clade of *A. cerberus* Arteaga *et al.* 2017, *A. iridescens* Peracca, 1896, *A. esepe* Arteaga *et al.* 2017, *A. microrhynchus* (Cope, 1868) and *A. dunni* Savage, 1955 with a TMRCA of 15.19 Myr age (95% HDP = 11.89-16.64); clade of *A. zidoki*, *A. savage* and *A. modestus* (Boulenger, 1894) + *A. paudicens* Depax, 1910, *A. typhon* Passos, Mueses-Cisneros, Lynch & Fernandes, 2009 and *A. gigas* Myers & Schargel, 2006 with TMRCA of 13.05 Myr age (95% HDP = 9.04-17.67). All of these diverged 19.46 Myr ago (95 % HDP = 16.44-22.68) of clade constitutes for *A. albuquerquei* Cunha & Nascimento, 1983, *A. elaps* Günther, 1858 and *A.*

latifrons Günther, 1868 with a TMRCA age of 16.76 Myr (95 % HDP = 13.22-20.61), clade of *A. riveroi* Roze, 1961, *A. flammigerus* (Boie, 1827) and *A. torquatus* Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854 with a TMRCA of 14.66 Myr (95 % HDP = 11.55-17.86), clade of *A. steyermarki* Roze, 1958 and *A. favae* (De Filippi, 1840) + *Atractus* sp., *A. boimirin* Passos, Prudente & Lynch, 2016 and *A. badius* (Boie, 1827) with a TMRCA age of 15.29 Myr (95 % HDP = 12.22-16.62) and the clade with a TMRCA of 14.94 Myr ago (95 % HDP = 12.09-18.01) constitutes for *A. atlas* Passos, Scanferla, Melo-Sampaio, Brito, & Almendariz, 2018 and *A. touzeti* Schargel *et al.* 2013 + *A. ecuadorensis* Savage, 1955, *A. orcesi* Savage, 1955 and *A. duboisi* (Boulenger, 1880) + *A. discovery* Arteaga *et al.* 2022 and *A. resplendens* Werner, 1901, and that diverged of clade *A. zgap* Arteaga, Quezada, Vieira & Guayasamín, 2022 + *A. ukupacha* Melo-Sampaio, Passos, Prudente, Venegas & Torres-Carvajal, 2021 and *Atractus* sp. + *A. snethlageae* Cunha & Nascimento, 1983, *A. pachacamac* Melo-Sampaio, Passos, Prudente, Venegas & Torres-Carvajal, 2021 and *Atractus* sp. + *A. schach* (Boie, 1827), *A. trefauti* Melo-Sampaio, Passos, Fouquet, Costa-Prudente & Torres-Carvajal, 2019 and *A. dapsilis* Melo-Sampaio, Passos, Fouquet, Costa-Prudente & Torres-Carvajal, 2019. **Lineage C**: TMRCA of 20.18 Myr (95 % HDP = 16.92-23.53), where the clade *A. major* Boulenger, 1894, *A. arangoi* Prado, 1940, *A. fuliginosus* (Hallowell, 1845), *Atractus* aff. *insipidus* and *Atractus* sp. diverged 19.26 Myr ago (95 % HDP = 16.1-22.86) of the clade that includes *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. ventrimaculatus* + *A. trilineatus* Wagler, 1828 with a TMRCA age of 17.18 Myr (95% HDP = 13.61-20.87); while all of these diverged 20.18 Myr ago (95% HDP = 16.92-23.53) of clade *A. roulei* Despax, 1910, *A. michaelbalsani* and *A. carrioni* + *A. taphorni* and *A. emigdioi* + *A. vittatus* and *A. matthewi* + *A. erythromelas*, *Atractus* sp. and *A. meridensis*. With Venezuelan Andean clade of *A. emigdioi* and *A. taphorni* with a TMRCA age of 3.59 Myr (95 % HDP = 1.92-5.47); Venezuelan Andean clade of *A. mariselae*, *Atractus* sp. and *A. mijaresi* + *A. erythromelas*, *Atractus* sp. and *A. meridensis* Esqueda & La Marca, 2005 with a TMRCA age of 9.55 Myr (95 % HDP = 1.1-12.16); Ecuadorian Pacific clade of *A. roulei*, *A. michaelbalsani* Arteaga *et al.* 2022 and *A. carrioni* Parker, 1930 with a TMRCA age of 14.31 Myr (95 % HDP = 10.96-17.75).

Figure 2. Bayesian inference tree along with divergence time estimation under the topology. Best posterior probability values symbol > 0.95 (color circles, see legend). Bars on nodes represent the 95% credibility interval of divergence times.

Uncorrected interspecific genetic p-distances are presented for Cytb (Supp._1_8–9) and ND4 (Supp._1_10–11). In the case of Cytb, mean genetic distances of the Venezuelan mimic species range of 0.072887 ± 0.009654 (*A. erythromelas* vs. *A. meridensis*), 0.078595 ± 0.009556 (*A. erythromelas* vs. *Atractus* sp.) and 0.059436 ± 0.009067 (*A. meridensis* vs. *Atractus* sp.). The sister species *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. ventrimaculatus* possess mean genetic distance range from 0.050887 ± 0.008151 . Meanwhile, uncorrected p-distances between each taxon/lineage within *Atractus* range from 1.05 % (*A. snethlageae* vs. *A. pachacamac*) to greater than 17 % (*A. esepe* vs. *A. carrioni*). For ND4, mean genetic distances varied from 0.05393 ± 0.00933 (*A. erythromelas* vs. *A. meridensis*), 0.06073 ± 0.01055 (*A. erythromelas* vs. *A. meridensis*) and 0.04197 ± 0.00896 (*A. meridensis* vs. *Atractus* sp.); in *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. ventrimaculatus* average 0.06851 ± 0.01075 . At the genus level, mean genetic distances average 1.1 % (*A. snethlageae* vs. *A. pachacamac*) and 17 % (*A. ventrimaculatus* vs. *A. vittatus*).

Ecological approach

According to the consistency and quality of environmental modeling for the species studied, the final ROC curve of the model for each of the scenarios showed AUC values between 0.99 for the training data and 0.97–0.99 for the test data (Supp._1_12), indicating that the Maxent model effectively predicted the distribution with highly suitable environments for *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. ventrimaculatus* for the three scenarios (Fig. 3). In comparison, according to the statistics of True Skills (TSS) and the operational characteristics of Reception (ROC), they obtained values above 0.72–0.96 and 0.58–1, respectively (Supp._1_13). In the current scenario (Fig. 3A), *A. ventrimaculatus* occupies an area of 2,212.749 km² and is mostly distributed in the montane rainforest of the Northern Andes and intervened areas, with a suitable area of 494.109 km² (Suppl._1_14). Meanwhile, *A. ochrosetrus* occupies an area of 751.905 km² and is mostly distributed in montane rainforest of the Northern Andes, with a suitable area of 429.66 km² (Supp._1_14). The projection for both taxa for the LGM 21 Kya climate indicated that the distribution of adequate environments for this species could have been more limited at the time (Fig. 3B), unlike the Pliocene 3.2 Myr, during which an expansion of their distribution area is observed (Fig. 3C). Our sorted and verified data suggest that the altitudinal range from *A. ventrimaculatus* varies between 1160–

2684 m (494.1 km² would correspond to moderate-high suitability areas between 2000–2500 m a.s.l.) and *A. ochrosetrus* occurs between 1077–3275 m (666 km² would correspond to moderate-high suitability areas between 1500–2500 m a.s.l.).

In the Maxent model for each scenario, the Jackknife method was used, and the results may show the weight of different environmental factors that affect the suitability of the habitat for *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. ventrimaculatus* (Supp._1_15). On the other hand, one of the main determining environmental factors in the potential distribution in the three scenarios was Bio_1 variable, in *A. ochrosetrus* with 49.7–62.2 % (Supp._1_16) and *A. ventrimaculatus* with 46.5–69.7 % (Supp._1_16).

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) revealed that the first three components together explain more than 86–98 % of the variation in the bioclimatic variables across all predicted scenarios. In the current scenario (Fig. 4A), moderate overlap between the niches was observed ($D = 0.68$, $I = 0.77$). The PERMANOVA test showed significant differences between the niche centroids ($R^2 = 0.14$, $p = 0.005$) (Supp._1_17). The equivalence ($p = 0.0139$) and similarity tests reveal asymmetry: *A. ochrosetrus* cannot occupy the niche of *A. ventrimaculatus* ($p = 0.0024$), while the opposite is not significant ($p = 0.175$). The variables that contribute most to the segregation are the precipitation of the wettest month (BIO13), the annual mean temperature (BIO1), and the temperature seasonality (BIO4) (Suppl._1_18). During the LGM (Fig. 4B), the overlap was null ($D \approx 0$, $I \approx 0$), and the differences were highly significant ($R^2 = 0.68$, $p = 0.001$) (Supp._1_17). The equivalence ($p \approx 2.9e-09$) and similarity tests suggest that the niches were completely divergent, with a slight possibility of reciprocal occupation only by *A. ventrimaculatus* ($p = 0.0047$). During this period, the niche was primarily structured by BIO13, BIO17 (precipitation of the driest quarter), and BIO12 (annual precipitation) (Supp._1_18). While during the Pliocene (Fig. 4C), low overlap was also observed ($D = 0.04$, $I = 0.04$) with significant differences ($R^2 = 0.49$, $p = 0.001$) (Supp._1_17). The dominant variables were BIO1, BIO13, and BIO4, reflecting a segregation associated with both temperature and water availability (Supp._1_18). These results suggest a historical divergence in the use of climatic space, possibly influenced by differential adaptation to past climates and ecological constraints.

According to our ENM for the current scenario, *A. ochrosetrus* had an EOO of 273.19 km² and AOO of 28 km² (geocat EOO = 274.454 km² and AOO = 40 km² to 2 km; Supp._1_19A), while *A.*

ventrimaculatus had an EOO = 157.31 km² and AOO = 36 km² (geocat EOO= 158.232 km² and AOO = 48 km² to 2 km; Supp._1_19B).

Figure 3. Geographic projection of the ecological niche model built for *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. ventrimaculatus* into the climatic scenarios explored. (A) Present scenery; (B) LGM scenery, 21 Kya and (C) Pliocene scenery, 3.2 Myr. The environmental suitability predicted is depicted without umbral defined.

Figure 4. The orthogonal projection of the first three principal components constructed from climatic characterizations of the geographic distribution from *A. erythromelas* and *A. meridensis* for each of the modeled scenarios. The points correspond to the localities characterized based on 6–7 bioclimatic variables and the ellipses correspond to the volumes built from the climatic niches of *A. ochrosetrus* (yellow ellipse) and *A. ventrimaculatus* (violet ellipse). Percentage of explained variance accounted for by each principal component is depicted.

Morphological approach

Historical background between *A. pamplonensis* Amaral, 1937 and *Atractus mijaresi* Esqueda & La Marca, 2005

The species was described based on six specimens and formally accepted in publication as Amaral (1937) (Passos *et al.* 2024: 57). It was later mentioned by Peters & Orejas-Miranda (1970) and Pérez-Santos & Moreno (1988), both of whom noted that the species exhibits a ventral scale count in males >170–183 and in females >170–184 and which corresponds to the original description (Amaral 1937: 220). Meanwhile, *A. mijaresi* was described by Esqueda & La Marca (2005: 16–17, Fig. 15) starting from an adult female of Mucurubá, Mérida state. Conveniently, Passos *et al.* (2024: 57) consider this latter species a synonym of *A. pamplonensis*. Even though their discriminant analysis clearly identifies differences in the ventral scale count in males, they argue that overlap in other characters justifies said decision. However, in light of new evidence molecular (DNAm and DNAn), morphology of the hemipenis and coloration in life allows for the clear distinction of these populations restricted to the northwest of the middle–high basin of the Chama River as a valid taxon, being sufficient arguments to understand that its nomenclatural decision lacks support and was clearly premature.

In fact, some comparative examples in the genus: *A. hoogmoedi* was described by Prudente & Passos

(2010), being the only distinctive character with respect to *A. zidoki* Gasc & Rodrigues, 1979, the bifurcation of the spermaticus sulcus and some details in the hemipenial ornamentation. Moreover, they consider such evidence of a cryptic condition, but there is no phylogenetic analysis to support it. When comparing *A. boulengerii* Peracca, 1896 with *A. medusa* Passos, Mueses-Cisneros, Lynch & Fernandes, 2009, the most distinctive character is the ventral count in males 133 vs. 176–189 and geographically close (Passos *et al.* 2009e). When comparing *A. multidentatus* (Fig. 10M) with *A. emigdioi*, the only clear difference is the maxillary teeth count (Passos *et al.* 2009b; Passos *et al.* 2024). When comparing *A. ronnie* Passos, Fernandes & Borges-Nojosa, 2007 with *A. natans* Hoogmoed & Prudente, 2003, the one distinctive character that sets her apart is venter uniformly creamish white vs. venter with a wide central black stripe of irregular width (Passos *et al.* 2007). When comparing *A. gaigeae* (Savage, 1955) with *A. alphonsehogeii* Cunha & Nascimento, 1983 and *A. collaris* Peracca, 1897, the only distinguishing feature is the ventral count 200–214 in females and 184–198 in males vs. 163–176 in females and 150–162 in males, and 167–186 in females and 145–178 in males, respectively (Passos *et al.* 2018).

On the other hand, Schargel & García-Pérez (2002) indicated as *Atractus* sp. a material from La Carbonera, Mérida state (MCNG R-1898-1904), not mentioned by Passos *et al.* (2024), but in their examined material indicated other material from the

same area as *A. pamplonensis*, but deposited in CVULA (here recognized as *A. mijaresi*).

Historical background between *Atractus ventrimaculatus* Boulenger, 1905 and *A. ochrosetrus* Esqueda & La Marca, 2005

Atractus ventrimaculatus was described by Boulenger (1905) based on several specimens deposited in the British Museum, although in his description the author only indicated a measurement of total length and tail, there was no designation of the holotype or lectotype, so these specimens constitute syntypes (ICZN 1999, art. 72.3). Regarding the type locality, the author indicated “Several specimens from Merida (1630 m.) and Fuqueros (2500 m.), Venezuela, collected by Mr. Briceño”. Although the “Fuqueros” locality has been mentioned for *Anadia bitaeniata* (Harris & Ayala 1987) and *Bolitoglossa orestes* Brame & Wake, 1962 (Fermin *et al.* 2012), its veracity can be difficult to verify so far. Meanwhile, in 1904 the districts that made up the Venezuelan federation had come together to form several states, including Mérida, so the locality “Merida” indicated by Boulenger (1905) is also considered ambiguous due to the extension or precision of the data, since it cannot be demonstrated whether it refers to the city or the state already consolidated at that time (Monzón-Briceño 2005). Recently, Passos *et al.* (2024: 37) erroneously indicated “Fuqueros” instead of “Fuqueros” for the lectotype BMNH 1946.1.7.7 (BMNH 1905.5.31.74; Wallach *et al.* 2014), designated according to them by Roze (1961: 108). When reviewing this last author, he only noted “We have examined the type of this species in BM 1905. 5. 31. 74”, which should be considered an assignment of the lectotype (ICZN 1999, art. 74.5). Then the type locality of the species would be the one determined by the lectotype (ICZN 1999, art. 76.2), in this case “Fuqueros”, not indicated by Roze (1961: 108), but if Roze (1966: 90). However, this locality is considered uncertain, being difficult to locate geographically and despite the fact that there is a suggestion to select the lectotype based on the verification of its locality for assignments after 1999 and not before (ICZN 1999, art. 74.7., recommendation 74E); Without an option to invalidate a lectotype with a doubtful locality, the remaining syntypes become paralectotypes (see Passos *et al.* 2024). Consequently, only the assignment of a neotype (ICZN 1999, art. 75.3.1) remains to stabilize the type locality of the species, allowing the establishment of a coherent distribution pattern and geographic limits with additional data. Specimen BM 1946.1.5.15 was

indicated by Passos *et al.* (2005: 218) as the paratype, later by Passos *et al.* (2009d: 403) as the holotype, and subsequently by Natera-Mumaw *et al.* (2015: 126); This action is erroneous, since the recognition of the holotype can only be established by the author in its original description (ICZN 1999, art. 73.1.3 and art. 74.6). While Wallach *et al.* (2014: 83) indicated this taxon for the state of Zulia based on the record made by Rojas-Runjaic *et al.* (2007), Natera-Mumaw *et al.* (2015: 126) consider it erroneous and retain the endemic status of the species for the state of Mérida; and although Montes-Correa *et al.* (2017: 36) continued to indicate *A. ventrimaculatus* for the serranía of Perijá, in Passos *et al.* (2024: 43) they did not even mention it. On the other hand, these last authors erroneously identify specimen CVULA 7381 as this species, when in fact it corresponds to an undescribed species with 17 dorsal scales at midbody (Esqueda and col. in prep.); they also point out three specimens from Manzano Alto and Tapa Azul slope corresponding to a private collection “CBA”, without giving further details, and we assume they refer to César Barrio Amorós (I consider such records doubtful until evidence exists to the contrary); they also misspelled the locality “Humbo Peak: (EBRG 4052)”, its correct locality being Humboldt Peak, Sierra Nevada National Park.

Otherworldly and disconcerting, the amount errors referred to toponymy, identities of specimens, scientific names and locality indicated in the article of Passos *et al.* (2024). With reference to the comparison of *A. ventrimaculatus* and *A. ochrosetrus*, the following: Esqueda & La Marca (2005) described *A. ochrosetrus* whose type locality is VENEZUELA: Mérida State: Tovar Municipality: on the road from Bailadores to “La Y”, El Delgadito, approx. 2600 m.a.s.l., 08°13'06"N, 71°52'26" W (see ICZN 2012, art. 76.1); erroneously indicated as “from the Tovar-Guaraque Highway, municipality of Tovar, sate of Mérida, Venezuela” by Passos *et al.* (2024: 37, p. 122); similarly, specimen ULABG 2409 indicated as *A. ventrimaculatus* and coming from “Táchira: Betania” (Passos *et al.* 2024: 40 and 122), its correct locality is Betania, between El Molino and La “Y” via Estanques-Canaguá, Mérida state, Venezuela (ULABG database, where Luis Felipe Esqueda was Ad Honorem curator of the collection for several years); It is curious but Enrique La Marca, director of the ULABG collection and who in all my years in the collection never provided an incorrect location, does not appear in the acknowledgments.

According to Passos *et al.* (2024) *A. ochrosetrus* should be considered a synonym of *A. ventrimaculatus* due to a misinterpretation of the character states: (1) they point out that the maxillary teeth of the holotype and paratype in Esqueda & La Marca (2005) are 12-14 and not eight as previously stated. We have examined six specimens from the topotypic locality and they present 8-10 maxillary teeth, last tooth reduced (see Fig. 8C-D), while we have examined five specimens of *A. ventrimaculatus* that present 12 maxillary teeth (Fig. 5F-H); (2) these authors point out that the pattern in *A. ventrimaculatus* is highly variable and that the coloration of *A. ochrosetrus* is an oversimplification of the polychromatic one in *A. ventrimaculatus*, based on the interpretation of preserved material and not information on coloration in life. Then, this unsupported argument, not is true: (A) information from Boulenger (1905) and Roze (1966) regarding coloration is based on preserved material. The authors point out the frequency of a dark vertebral line, continuous or discontinuous, but in none of the cases two dark, continuous dorsolateral lines, 1 ½ scales wide, a detail present in all the *A. ochrosetrus* adults that we have observed and notable in the holotype (Esqueda & La Marca 2005: 19, Fig. 19), but not discussed by Passos *et al.* (2024); (B) in *A. ventrimaculatus* there is frequently a melanic dorsal pattern in life, with the dorsal region being uniformly black, sometimes with small yellow spots, but without a vertebral line being appreciated (absent or not visibly in life, unpublished data LFE 2021; see also La Marca & Soriano 2004: 95, Fig. 42). Another less common pattern consists of a brown to greyish-brown background, without a vertebral line, but with narrow, discontinuous, paravertebral yellow lines bordered by black (Natera-Mumaw *et al.* 2015: 150, Fig. 148), or there may be a brown background with dark and light stretch marks arranged longitudinally (Lancini 1979, Esqueda & La Marca 2005). A third pattern presents a dark brown or greyish-brown back with dark spots, irregularly dispersed, without a defined design. Finally, we found a male specimen with a yellowish-brown back, with scattered dark spots (unpublished data, LFE 2021); (C) in accordance with Passos *et al.* (2024), the information on the hemipenes of both species given by Esqueda & La Marca (2005) is wrong, although they conveniently forget to point out the information provided by Esqueda *et al.* (2007: 92), who correct it and point out some additional details. When reviewing the article by Passos *et al.* (2024: 42), an anecdotal detail reiterated in other descriptions is the absence of a voucher regarding the description of the hemipenis. On the other hand, its description has

similar and/or different details to the description indicated by Schargel & Castoe (2003) for *A. ventrimaculatus*, as follows: (A) both descriptions point out the slightly bilobed condition, especially noticeable in the drawing provided by Schargel & Castoe (2003). Although this information is not entirely certain (see later in their redescrptions), the important thing is that the image provided by Esqueda *et al.* (2007: 92, Fig. 5) of the only hemipenis available in *A. ochrosetrus* and that demonstrate its unicapitate condition (see for interpretation of hemipenis, Dowling & Savage 1961, Zaher 1999), conveniently not discussed by Passos *et al.* (2024); (B) although Schargel & Castoe reported the hemipenis as unicapitate in *A. ventrimaculatus*, Passos *et al.* (2024) recognized it as semicapitate, without providing any record of the specimen or drawings or photos; (C) Schargel & Castoe (2003) noted that the organ is bare towards the basal region, a detail omitted in the description of Passos *et al.* (2024); (D) according to Passos *et al.* (2024), *A. ventrimaculatus* would have a capitulum located proximal to sulcus spermaticus bifurcation with similar length as hemipenis body, while the drawing provided by Schargel & García-Pérez (2002: 720, Fig. A) shows a capitulum with greater extension than the body of the hemipenis and would start a little below the bifurcation of the spermatic sulcus, although the rounded shape of the capitulum and the spinulate fringes are not observed in *A. ochrosetrus* (Esqueda *et al.* 2007: 92, Fig. 5), evenly not discussed by Passos *et al.* (2024).

Species account

Atractus ventrimaculatus Boulenger, 1905 (Figs. 6A-C)

Atractus ventrimaculatus. Boulenger, 1905; Annals and Magazine of Natural History 15:455.

Atractus ventrimaculatus. Passos *et al.* (2024, 32:1-123).

LECTOTYPE

Adult male, BMNH 1946.1.7.7, (formerly BMNH 1905.5.31.74; Wallach *et al.* 2014), collected by S. Briceño at locality of Fugueros (not traced, ca. 2,500 m a.s.l.), state of Mérida, Venezuela. Lectotype designated by Roze (1961:108). **Note:** Boulenger indicated “fuqueros”, and in no case “Fugueros” as mentioned Passos *et al.* (2024) (see Roze 1966).

PARALECTOTYPES

Five specimens (as stated in the BMNH database): 1946.1.5.12-15, all collected by S. Briceño at municipality of Mérida (08°36'N, 71°09'W; ca. 1,500 m a.s.l.), state of Mérida, Venezuela (Figs. 29-30 in Passos *et al.* 2024). **Note:** In the original description, only appears "Several specimens from Merida (1630 m.) and Fuqueros (2500 m.), Venezuela, collected by Señor Briceño".

NEOTYPE (NEW ASSIGNMENT)

Adult female, MZUC 48014 (field number LFE 140). Collected by Luis Felipe Esqueda, Santos Bazó and Alexis Peña, July 4, 2021, deposited in the Zoology Museum of the Faculty of Natural and Oceanographic Sciences, University of Concepción, Chile (MZUC). 1.6 km N from Truchicultura Monterrey, El Valle-La Culata road, Mérida, Mérida state, Venezuela, altitude 2477 m a.s.l., 8°41'4.61"N and 71°7'56.51"W.

Definition and diagnosis

(1) 15 scale rows dorsal to midbody, without reduction; (2) maximum total length 402.37 mm in males and 413.62 in females; (3) sublabials or pseudo-chinchiels separate with each other, the distance is greater than the suture of the first pair of infralabials; (4) unilobed, unicapitate, semicalyculate hemipenis; (5) 11-12 maxillary teeth, the last one not reduced; usually a weakly defined lateral process, arranged horizontally to the maxilla and situated between the 6th to 9th teeth; (6) supralabial in contact with anterior temporal and postocular is wider, with its upper margins asymmetrical; (7) 8(4,5) or 7(3,4) supralabials; (8) seven infralabials, four in contact with genials; (9) postnasal similar in size to prenasal; (10) rostral slightly visible from above; in frontal view subtrapezoidal, as high as wide or wider, narrow apical edge, < 0.5 distance between nostrils and concave lateral margins; (11) first supralabial small, higher than wide, short-moderate supralabial-rostral contact; (12) loreal moderate-long, in contact with three or two supralabials; (13) frontal scute irregularly hexagonal, usually longer than wide; (14) moderate internasals, longer than wide, two or less of the prefrontal suture; (15) moderate- snout, frontal-rostral distance 1.93-3.44 mm; (16) head indifferent from the neck, strongly compressed in dorsal view, being subtriangular and with a rounded snout, relation AEE-AEN 43.2-58.9 % in females, 37.4-52.6 %; (17) in life, very frequently the dorsal pattern observed has a melanistic background, in which the black vertebral line is indistinguishable, only present or absent in preserved specimens.

Other patterns have a light brown, grayish-brown, and yellowish-brown dorsal background, with dark spots sometimes bordered in black and distributed longitudinally, a black vertebral line is not noticeable. In none of the detected patterns are there one or more dorsolateral lines; only in certain individuals are there two narrow yellow paravertebral lines; (18) in life, ventral surface has an intense yellowish background, with extensive black spots that almost cover the entire surface on certain sides; (19) usually yellow stretch marks on the dorsocaudals, ventral surface of the tail yellow, moderate or strongly stained with black; (20) thick tail, short-moderate and ends in a blunt tip, 11-15.7% SVL in males and 4.7-11.4% SVL in females; (21) 138-153 ventrals in males, 147-161 in females; (22) 18-22 subcaudals in males, 13-20 in females.

Description on museum material

Maximum total length in males 402.37 mm and in 413.62 mm in females (SVL 246.68-364.778 in males and 282.3-382.6 in females); tail length 28.43-42.29 mm (n = 10) and 17.87-36.44 (n = 10); head length in males 8.43-12.04 (n = 10, = 10.37 ± 1.4159) in males and 7.12-12.04 (n = 10, = 10.01 ± 1.5244) in females; head width 6.59-9.95 mm (n = 10, = 8.11 ± 1.17) and 5.78-8.9 mm (n = 10, = 7.75 ± 0.98097) in females. Head in dorsal view: longer than wide, undifferentiated from the neck, compressed (ID/IND relation 40.1-52.6 % in males and 37.4-58.9 % in females; rounded snout. Rostral slightly visible from above, in frontal view subtrapezoidal, as wide as high or slightly wider, concave lateral margins, narrow apical edge (< 0.5 times END) and exceeds the imaginary straight line between the nostrils (Fig. 5D); two internasals, higher than wide, internasal suture 2.4-4.7 times in relation to the prefrontal suture, no sinastria; two prefrontals, frontal-rostral distance shorter than frontal length, prefrontal-postnasal contact shorter than the eye-prefrontal contact; frontal scute irregularly hexagonal, longer than wide (n = 15) or wider than long (n = 5) (Fig. 5A); supraoculars tetragonal, much wider posteriorly; two parietals, parietal suture 0.29-0.34 of HL in males and 0.29-0.41 of HL in females. In lateral view: circular eye, 1.26-1.85 mm HED in males and 0.97-1.64 mm in females; elongated snout, END 2.38-3.55 mm in males and 2.27-3.43 mm in females; prenasal and postnasal more or less similar in size, nostril situated above the prenasal edge; postnasal-loreal contact wider than eye-loreal contact; loreal elongated, higher anteriorly, in contact with two or three supralabials (usually three); two postoculars, the upper quadrangular and widened, the lower

elongated (Fig. 5B); temporal formula 1+2, the first temporal well elongated, almost equal to END, short first postocular-temporal contact and wide second postocular contact; 8(4,5), 8 (3,4) or 7(3,4) supralabials; first supralabial higher than wide, barely differentiated in size compared to the second, short or moderate supralabial-rostral contact; supralabial that contacts with anterior temporal and pentagonal postocular usually widened, with its upper margins asymmetrical. Ventrally, mental subtriangular, wider than long; seven infralabials, four in contact with the pair of genials (Fig. 5C); sublabials or pseudo-chinschields separated, spacing greater than or equal to the suture of the first pair of infralabials; genials elongated, suture 0.64-0.95 times longer than END in males and 0.44-0.9 times longer than in females (less common, shorter than END); 4-5 gulars; 1-3 preventrals; 138-153 ventrals in males ($n = 11$, $= 147.27 \pm 4.7768$) 147-161 in females ($n = 10$, $= 152.7 \pm 4.9187$); 18-22 subcaudals in males ($n = 10$, $= 20.2 \pm 1.5491$) and 13-20 in females ($n = 10$, $= 15.88 \pm 2.7131$). Thick tail, 4-8 dorsocaudals at the level of the sixth subcaudal; entire cloacal scale, 1.76-4.02 mm long in males and 2.52-4.26 mm in females. 15 dorsal scales at the midbody, without reduction; body thickness at the midbody 10.5-15.87 mm in males ($n = 10$, $= 11.7 \text{ mm} \pm 2.0377$) and 8.76-16.09 in females ($n = 10$, $= 12.5 \text{ mm} \pm 2.1328$).

Maxillar bone

Between teeth 1-2 narrow, then it can be somewhat or well arched; 4.49-5.4 mm long; lateral process moderately defined or pronounced, but horizontally arranged with respect to the bone, located between the seventh and ninth tooth (Fig. 5E-G); 11-12 maxillary teeth ($n = 5$), curved, the last slightly more spaced (not reduced).

Hemipenis (everted organs $n = 1$, MZUC 48013)

Unilobed, unicapitate and semicalyculate organ (Fig. 5H). Well-defined capitulum, extensively larger than the rest of the hemipenis, completely encircled by spinulate flounces. Body of the hemipenis provided with rows of long spines, with insertions of small spines; capitular groove definite (in sulcate and asulcate region); bifurcation of sulcus spermaticus occurs on the capitulum. Asulcate region covered with the same pattern of long and small spines, but with a higher frequency of long spines. The base of the hemipenis is nude, with only small spinules insertions; basal naked pocket not defined.

Coloration in life

The information described by Boulenger (1905) and Roze (1966) is based on preserved specimens. La Marca & Soriano (2004, Fig. 42) indicated that the dorsal coloration is uniform, dark brown or almost black, and the belly is yellow with numerous dark brown spots. Whereas Esqueda & La Marca (2005) noted the belly as yellow with black spots. This taxon frequently exhibits a melanistic pattern on the dorsal side of the body and head (Fig. 6A), an inconspicuous or absent black vertebral line (observable in preserved specimens); sometimes, towards the dorsocaudal region, some yellow striated spots are observed (Fig. 6B). The ventral surface of the body has a bright yellow background, heavily spotted with black; immaculate or weakly laterally spotted cloacal scale; yellow subcaudals, weakly or heavily spotted with dark brown or black. A pattern that had not yet been observed in life, the preserved specimens exhibit a dorsum adorned with dark brown spots, irregularly dispersed, conspicuous, cream-margined, and sometimes concentrated laterally or towards the vertebral region (see Esqueda & La Marca 2005: Fig. 24, Passos *et al.* 2024: Fig. 29). Dorsal coloration of the head similar to the body background, the supralabials intense yellow, with a wider spot behind the eye (Fig. 6C). In certain individuals, yellow stretch marks have been observed in life towards the dorsocaudal region (Natera-Mumaw *et al.* 2015: Fig. 148), similar to those observed in *Atractus matthewi* Barrio-Amorós & Markezich, 2004 (LFE unpublished data 2021).

Distribution and natural history

This taxon is considered endemic to the cordillera de Mérida. It is found in sympatry with *A. erythromelas* Boulenger, 1903 along the middle basin of the Chama River, heading towards La Culata from Jají, passing through the city of Mérida (Chorros de Milla and Santa Rosa above) and El Valle; then it exhibits some disjunct populations towards La Mucuy high towards the Sierra Nevada Park (Fig. 7). Altitudinally, it occupies the montane semideciduous forest floor and the Andean cloud forest, between 1700 and 3250 m. Here we define that the reference locality with respect to its topotypical area, but avoiding erroneous or very general localities, is the region that includes El Valle, specifically towards Truchicultura San Javier and its surroundings, and that varies in altitude from 2000 to 2500 m asl.

Figure 5. Morphological details related to *Atractus ventrimaculatus*. Specimen MZUC 48014, (A) dorsal view of head; (B) lateral view of head; ventral view of head and (D) frontal view of the frontal scale. Specimen MZUC 48013, internal and external view of the maxilla (E1-E2). Specimen MZUC 48015, internal and external view of the maxilla (F1-F2) and Specimen MZUC 48016, internal and external view of the maxilla (G1-G2). Specimen MZUC 48013, sulcate and asulcate view of hemipenis (H₁-H₂).

Figure 6. Details of the coloration in life of *A. ventrimaculatus*: (A) specimen MZUC 48018, posterior to the Truchicultura Monterrey, way El Valle-La Culata, Mérida state, Venezuela. Dorsal view of the body and head showing the melanic pattern. © Luis Felipe Esqueda; (B) adult individual s/n, city of Mérida, with the brown-yellowish pattern, without lines and with scattered spots by Daniel Quihua; (C) specimen MZUC 48015, dorsal view of head showing the contact of supralabials with loreal by Luis Felipe Esqueda. Details of the coloration in life of *A. ochrosetrus*: (D₁-D₂) adult female collected 9.3 km on the EL Zumbador-Queniquea road. Dorsal and ventral views of body and head by Enrique La Marca; (E₁-E₂) specimens MZUC 48020-21, collected in La M (curve), after Bailadores near of the road way Las Porqueras, Mérida state, Venezuela. Dorsal and ventral view of the body and head by Luis Felipe Esqueda; (F) individual s/n, found dead on the road near the Páramo Batallón y La Negra National Park, Táchira state. Dorsal view shows the presence of dorsolateral lines by Jairo Rodríguez; (G₁-G₂) specimen MZUC 48022, collected in Potrero Grande, after the M (curve), way Las Porqueras, Mérida state, Venezuela. Lateral view of body and view of head and anterior third of body, the presence of dorsolateral and paravertebral lines is observed. © Luis Felipe Esqueda.

Figure 7. Map of the cordillera de Mérida showing the distribution from *A. ochrosetrus*, *A. ventrimaculatus* and *A. mijaresi*. Base vegetation map © Eulogio Chacón Moreno. Chama basin intramontane © Rayner Castro <https://www.maps.com/>

So far, we have not observed any individuals active during the day. Our findings have been under moderately sized rocks (>20 kg), in anthropized environments, consisting of high-altitude grasslands (e.g., kikuyu). Near the San Javier Trout Farm, El Valle, Mérida state (2477 m asl., 8°41'4.61"N and 71°7'6.51"W), we found two specimens together MZUC 48017-48018 during the day under a rock (collected July 4, 2025). Another individual MZUC 48013 was found around an egg communal nest of *Anadia bitaeniata* Boulenger, 1903.

Conservation status

Niche modeling using MaxEnt yielded a predicted suitable distribution area for the species of 2,212.749 km², consisting mostly of montane rainforests of the northern Andes (494.109 km²) and intervened areas (515.592 km²) (Supplementary_1_Table 14). Our calculations in R according to IUCN, indicate an area EOO of 157.31 km² (geocat EOO = 158.232 km²) and AOO of 36 km² (geocat AOO = 48 km²), <https://geocat.iucnredlist.org/> (Supplementary_1_Table 19B). New field data and analysis demonstrate that the species exhibits isolated but abundant populations in the sampled localities. However, much of its area, which includes Andean montane semideciduous forests and Andean cloud forests, is highly fragmented and/or converted to high-altitude agrosilvopastorals systems, a situation that significantly impacts the water dynamics of these ecosystems (Ataroff &

Naranjo 2009). This ecogeographical scenario, together with the fact that these snakes feed exclusively on earthworms, can directly affect its diversity and population dynamics due to deforestation and conversion of their environments because it promotes inadequate edaphic conditions such as alkaline pH, fertility, quality of organic matter and alteration of soil properties such as physical-chemical (Hendrix *et al.* 2008), particularly in tropical mountain ecosystems that exhibit high rates of endemism in relatively small areas (Lavelle & Lapied 2003). In consequence, considering the IUCN conservation criteria (IUCN 2012) and the vulnerability index of reptile species (IVER, Esqueda & La Marca 2015), *Atractus ventrimaculatus* it must be included in the Vulnerable category according to criteria B2 (i,ii,iii,iv).

Atractus ochrosetrus Esqueda & La Marca, 2005 comb.nov. (Figs. 8D-G)

Atractus ochrosetrus. Esqueda & La Marca (2005:18).

Atractus ventrimaculatus. Passos *et al.* (2024:37).

HOLOTYPE

Adult male, ULABG 4698, coleccionado por Enrique La Marca el 12 de enero de 1999, depositado en la Colección de Anfibios y Reptiles, Laboratorio de Biogeografía, de la Universidad de

Los Andes, Mérida, Venezuela (Esqueda & La Marca 2005).

Definition and diagnosis

(1) 15 scale rows dorsal to midbody, without reduction; (2) maximum total length 376.75 mm in males and 421.65 in females; (3) usually sublabials or pseudo-chinchiels in contact with each other, when separate the width does not exceed the suture of the first pair of infralabials; (4) unilobed, semicapitate, semicalyculate hemipenis, capitular groove defined; (5) 8-10 maxillary teeth, usually last reduced; well-defined lateral process, disposed obliquely and located at the level of the 5-8 teeth; (6) normally supralabial in contact with anterior temporal and postocular is narrow, with its upper margins symmetrical; (7) frequently 8(4,5) supralabials, less common seven; (8) seven infralabials, four in contact with genials; (9) postnasal enlarged compared to prenasal; (10) rostral barely visible from above; in frontal view subtrapezoidal, taller than wide and slightly concave lateral margins; normally its apical edge is wide, > 0.5 the distance between nostrils and exceeds the imaginary straight line between nostrils; (11) first supralabial small, short supralabial-rostral contact; (12) loreal moderate-long, usually in contact with three supralabials; (13) frontal subtriangular or subhexagonal, longer than wide, convex anterior margins; (14) moderate internasal, longer than wide, two or less than prefrontal suture; (15) short-moderate snout, frontal-rostral distance 1.61-2.97 mm; (16) head indifferent from the neck, compressed in dorsal view, being subtriangular and with a rounded snout, relation ID-ND 38.4-44.3 % in females and 36.6-44.6 % in males; (17) in life, dorsal background frequently chestnut-yellow, less observed yellowish-brown or melanic, but with dorsolateral lines always visible. Black dorsolateral lines between the 3th to 5th dorsal row. Dark vertebral line defined, sometimes narrow and discontinuous and at other times wide and continuous. Apart from the dorsolateral lines, there may be narrow, continuous, or discontinuous black paravertebral lines, and sometimes bordered with cream; (18) pale or intense yellow ventral background of the body, heavily spotted with black, forming large intercalated spaces, rectangular and that sometimes occupy completely the scale in life. Yellow subcaudals, immaculate or weakly pigmented of black; (19) thick tail, short-moderate and ends in a blunt tip, 10.6-13.2 SVL in males and 6.6-9.1 SVL in females; (20) 144-152 ventrals in males, 146-156 in females; (21) 21-20 subcaudals in males, 14-18 in females.

The only species with certain similar attributes that inhabit the cordillera de Mérida are *A. taphorni* and *A. emigdioi*, but they are differentiated by both having a non-capitate (differentiated) and slightly bilobed hemipenis; usually seven supralabials and two in contact with the loreal vs. *A. ochrosetrus* which has a unicapitate (differentiated) and non-bilobed hemipenis; eight supralabials and three in contact with the loreal. On the other hand, our phylogenetic analysis suggests that the sister species of *A. ochrosetrus* is *A. ventrimaculatus*, which is differentiated by a usually melanic life pattern, with the vertebral line absent or inconspicuous in life (if exists, visible in preserved), without dorsolateral lines; sublabials or pseudo-chinchiels separated from each other and usually the subcaudals are moderately to heavily pigmented black (other comparative details, see Table 1).

Description on museum material

Maximum total length in males 376.75 mm and in 421.65 mm in females (SVL in males 288.6-340.57 mm and in females 290.71-370.87 mm); tail length 33.4-39.85 mm in males (n = 4) and 19.27-35.09 mm in females (n = 5); head length in males 8.06-11.12 mm (n = 4) and 7.73-11.9 mm in females (n = 5); head width in males 7-8.51 (n = 4) and 5.75-8.36 mm in females (n = 5). Head in dorsal view: longer than wide, undifferentiated from the neck, compressed (ID/IND relation 36.6-37.9 % in males and 38.4-43.6); rounded snout. Rostral barely visible from above, subtriangular or subtrapezoidal in frontal view, as high as wide, straight lateral margins, narrow apical edge that internasals (< 0.5 END) and well exceeding the imaginary straight line between nostrils (Fig. 8A₄-B₄); two internasals, longer than wide, internasal suture two or less than prefrontal suture, no sinastria; two prefrontals, widest posteriorly, frontal-rostral distance shorter than frontal length, prefrontal-postnasal contact shorter than eye-loreal contact (unusually similar); frontal shield subtriangular (Fig. 8A₁-B₁), with anterior margins straight or slightly convex, usually slightly longer than wide; two parietals, parietal suture longer than frontal length; two supraoculars elongate (~0.75 END). In lateral view: anteriorly arched or slightly arched, with a slightly rounded snout; frequently 8(4,5) supralabials (n = 12), less common 7(3,4) (n = 3); first supralabial small, supralabial-rostral contact short; supralabial in contact with anterior temporal and narrow postocular, with its upper margins symmetrical (Fig. 8A₂-B₂); postnasal irregularly hexagonal and vertically arranged, enlarged relative to prenasal; loreal elongate, slightly or more high anteriorly,

irregularly hexagonal and in contact with three supralabials (less common two); two postoculars, first rectangular, second the same or just slightly taller; temporal formula 1+2, without distinct supratemporals, 1st temporal elongated (~0.85 DON). Ventrally: mental subtriangular, wider than long; seven infralabials, four in contact with genials; frequently sublabials or pseudo-chinchiolds in contact with each other (n = 8, Fig. 8A₃-B₃), rarely separate, but their width does not exceed the suture of the single pair of infralabials (n = 6); 1-3 gulars and 1-3 prementals; ventrals in males 144-152 (n = 6, = 147.6 ± 3.7815) and 146-156 (n = 7, = 152.5 ± 4.1352) in females; subcaudals divided, count in males 20-22 (n = 6, = 21 ± 0.707) and 14-26 (n = 7, = 17.6 ± 4.3204) in females. Thick tail, 6.6-9.1 % in females and 10.6-13.2 % in males; eight dorsocaudals at the level of the sixth subcaudal; cloacal scale entire, 1.43-2.35 mm in males and 2.32-3.89 mm in females. 15 rows of dorsal scales in the middle of the body, without reduction towards the neck and tail.

Maxillar bone

Weakly arched, at the level of the widened lateral process; 3.8-4.7 mm in length; well-developed lateral process, situated between the sixth and eighth tooth, arranged obliquely with respect to the bone. 8-10 maxillary teeth, the last one reduced in size (Fig. 8C-D). Posterior projection visible.

Hemipenis (everted organs n = 1, MZUC 48023)

Unilobed, unicapitate, and semicalyculate organ. Well-defined capitulum, no longer than the body of the hemipenis, completely encircled by spinulate flounces (Fig. 8E). capitular groove definite (sulcate and asulcate sides); bifurcation of sulcus spermaticus occurs on the capitulum. Body of the hemipenis provided with rows of long spines, with insertions of small spines; nude basal region, except for a few small spinules and visible transverse plicae. Asulcate region covered of long spines, interspersed, and decreasing in size towards the hemipenial base.

Information of coloration (in life)

The dorsal pattern in common life observed in most of the collected specimens has a chestnut-yellow background with three longitudinal black lines. A vertebral stripe less than one scale wide, generally continuous to the end of the tail. On each side of the body, exist a wide black stripe (at least equivalent to a scale), situated between the second-

third or third-fourth dorsal rows, being able to be marginalized or not, on both sides, by a whitish line and that extends until the tail (Figs. 6D₁, F). In other individuals, we can observe two additional longitudinal black lines on the paravertebral region, continuous (Fig. 6E₁-E₂) or discontinuous (Fig. 6G₁-G₂), and that extend until the tail. The specimen ULABG 6745 (Fig. 6D₁), adult female, exhibits the common chestnut-yellow pattern with three longitudinal black lines, but the vertebral line between scales 7-9 is partitioned into continuous triangular strokes on the sides and the middle scale chestnut-yellow (here defined as a rhomboidal vertebral line with black lateral strokes and chestnut-yellow center). The specimen MZUC 48023 present a more melanistic coloration, although the dorsolateral lines are notably visible. Dorsal background of the head similar to the body; supralabials yellow with black spots above (Fig. 6G₁). The ventral region of the body is yellowish, heavily stained black, forming blocks of spots, irregularly interspersed, and sometimes covering the entire scale (Fig. 6D₂); cloacal shield yellowish, being able to be immaculate (n = 5) or spotted with black (n = 7). The yellowish subcaudals, usually immaculate or weakly speckled of black (n = 8), although less common can be a pattern moderate or strongly spotted of black (n = 4). The head is yellowish ventrally, with the first four infralabials, mental and genials strongly spotted with black.

Distribution and natural history

Like *A. ventrimaculatus*, it is an endemic species of the cordillera de Mérida. It extends southeast from the cordillera de Mérida, corresponding to the upper basins of the Uribante, El Valle, La Grita, and Mocoties rivers, Táchira and Mérida states, respectively (Fig. 7). Its altitudinal range varies between 2000-3000 m asl., corresponding to the Andean cloud forest, which has largely been converted into grasslands for high-altitude livestock farming. It is very likely that the elfin cloud forest also inhabits the drier slopes between 2000-2700 m asl. and the upper limit of the montane Andean semideciduous forest between 1500-2000 m asl. (Ataroff & Sarmiento 2004).

The species is found in sympatry with *A. tamaensis* and another *Atractus* sp., currently under study (Esqueda *et al.* in prep.), although less frequently. Although the material collected by us was under rocks, an adult female specimen ULABG 6745 was recently found run over in the morning, in a cloud forest, 9.3 km on the El Zumbador to Queniquea road (2705 m, 7°57'28.7"N and

72°4'21"W). Therefore, it is likely that the species is cathemeral, being active during the day or night.

Figure 8. Morphological details related to *Atractus ochrosetrus*. Specimen MZUC 48014, (A) dorsal view of head; (B) lateral view of head; ventral view of the and (D) frontal view of the frontal scale. Specimen MZUC 48013, internal and external view of the maxilla (F₁-F₂). Specimen MZUC 48015, internal and external view of the maxilla (G₁-G₂) and Specimen MZUC 48016, internal and external view of the maxilla (H₁-H₂). Specimen MZUC 48013, sulcate and asulcate view of hemipenis (I₁-I₂).

Conservation status

Niche modeling using MaxEnt yielded a predicted suitable distribution area for the species of 751.905 km², consisting mostly of montane rainforests of the northern Andes (429.66 km²) and intervened areas (85.932 km²) (Supplementary_1_Table 14). According to IUCN, an area EOO 273.19 (geocat EOO 274.454 km²) and AOO 28 km² (geocat AOO = 40 km²), <https://geocat.iucnredlist.org/editor> (Supplementary_1_Table 19A). New field data and analysis demonstrate that the species exhibits isolated but abundant populations in the sampled localities. However, much of its area, which includes Andean montane semideciduous forests and Andean cloud forests, is highly fragmented and/or converted to high-altitude agrosilvopastorals systems, a situation that significantly impacts the water dynamics of these ecosystems (Ataroff & Naranjo 2009). This eco-geographical scenario, together with the fact that these snakes feed exclusively on earthworms, can directly affect its diversity and population dynamics due to deforestation and conversion of their environments because it promotes inadequate edaphic conditions such as alkaline pH, fertility, quality of organic matter and alteration of soil properties such as physical-chemical (Hendrix *et al.* 2008), particularly in tropical mountain ecosystems that exhibit high rates of endemism in relatively small areas (Lavelle & Lapied 2003). In consequence, considering the IUCN conservation criteria (IUCN 2012) and the vulnerability index of reptile species (IVER, Esqueda & La Marca 2015), *Atractus ochrosetrus* it must be included in the Vulnerable category according to criteria B2 (i,ii,iii,iv).

Atractus mijaresi Esqueda & La Marca, 2005
comb.nov. (Figs. 10A-D)

Atractus mijaresi. Esqueda & La Marca (2005:16-17).

Atractus pamplonensis. Passos *et al.* (2024:51).

HOLOTYPE

Adult female, ULABG 4697, coleccionada por Néstor Jáuregui el 5 de mayo de 1997, depositada en la Colección de Anfibios y Reptiles, Laboratorio de Biogeografía, de la Universidad de Los Andes, Mérida, Venezuela (Esqueda & La Marca 2005).

TYPE LOCALITY

“Mucurubá, Mérida state”.

Definition and diagnosis

(1) 17 scale rows dorsal to midbody, without reduction; (2) maximum total length 331.9 mm in males and 377.8 in females; (3) rostral barely visible from above; subtrapezoidal frontal view, wider than high; short-moderate apical edge, <0.5 END, equal or barely exceeding the imaginary margin between nostrils; (4) first supralabial enlarged, moderate-ample supralabial-rostral contact; (5) head in dorsal view slightly differentiated from the neck, broad anteriorly and with the snout usually truncate, rarely rounded, and in lateral view with the snout subacuminate; (6) frontal hexagonal or subhexagonal, anterior margins slightly convex or straight, usually longer than wide; (7) loreal moderate, narrowed towards the eye and in contact with two supralabials; (8) 7(3,4) supralabials; (9) six infralabials, three scales in contact with genials; (10) eye-prefrontal contact wide and < than prefrontal-postnasal contact; (11) sublabials or pseudo-chinchiels well separated, as wide as the suture of the single pair of infralabials; (12) 4-5 gular scales; (12) 145-160 ventral in males and 157-170 in females; (13) 27-31 subcaudal in males and 24-30 in females; (14) in life the head is dorsally brown or uniformly olive-brown, with a lighter snout; dorsal background brown, copper-brown or uniform olive-brown, with barely distinguishable dark spots, circumscribed to the scale and irregularly arranged; (15) in life the ventral region has a pale yellow, pinkish or yellowish-orange background, lateroventrally spotted with brown or black, although the spots are not well defined; tail yellow, strongly mottled brown or black, cloacal scale yellow, weakly mottled; (16) six or seven dorsocaudals to sixth subcaudal scale; (17) thin tail, 9-11.3 % in females and 12.3-14.1 % in males; (18) moderately bilobed, semicapitate, semicalyculate hemipenis, subcylindrical lobes, capitular groove undefined and body of the hemipenis globular, where the capitulum is narrower; (19) 6-8, usually six maxillary teeth, well-developed lateral process, arranged horizontally to the bone between 5-6 teeth, last tooth visibly reduced in relation to the previous one.

Although geographically separated, but closest within the cordillera de Mérida, only *A. eriki*, *A. tamaensis* and *A. mariselae* share similarities, but differs from these in having a moderately bilobed, semicapitate hemipenis, subcylindrical lobes, capitulum narrower than the body of the hemipenis and capitular groove undefined vs. non-bilobed to poorly bilobed, with a wide capitulum in *A.*

tamaensis; slightly bilobed hemipenis, not subcylindrical lobes and capitular groove defined in *A. eriki* and slightly bilobed, not capitate hemipenis, not subcylindrical lobes and capitular groove undefined in *A. mariselae*. In the case of *A. pamplonensis*, this taxon has a slightly bilobed hemipenis, clavate lobes with a rounded apical edge and capitular groove defined (Passos *et al.* 2024). Other distinguishing characteristics between the species are listed in Table 1.

Description on museum material

Total maximum length in males 331.9 mm and in 377.9 in females (SVL in males 230.1-290.9 mm and in females 265.2-344.2 mm); tail length 31.2-41.05 mm in males (n = 5) and 24.5-33.7 mm in females (n = 5); head length in males 7.8-9.3 mm (n = 5) and 7.9-9.6 mm (n = 5) in females; head width in males 5.06-7.06 (n = 5) and 5.85-7.78 mm (n = 5) in females. Head in dorsal view longer than wide, slightly distinct from the neck; short, slightly truncated, or rounded and weakly compressed snout (ID-IND relation 27.1-40.9 % in males and 28.1-55.2 % in females). Rostral barely visible from above, in frontal view subtrapezoidal, wider than high, lateral margins usually concave; apical edge short (<0.5 END, Fig. 9A₄-B₄) and just reaching the imaginary straight line between nostrils; two internasals, variable in shape, but more commonly longer than wide or quadrangular, internasal suture 2 or 2 ½ times prefrontal suture, not sinastria; two prefrontals, slightly wider posteriorly; frontal shield hexagonal or subhexagonal, longer than wide, with convex or slightly convex anterior margins (Fig. 9A₁-B₁); small supraoculars (<0.75 END), irregularly pentagonal and wider posteriorly; two parietals, parietal suture 2.34-3.42 mm in males and 2.21-2.99 mm in females, longer than frontal length. In lateral view, head slightly arched after eye, snout truncated; 7(3,4)/7(3,4) supralabials, first supralabial moderate or elongated, higher than wide, short-moderate supralabial-rostral contact; two supralabials in contact with loreal (Fig. 9A₂-B₂); first supralabial in contact with the ocular orbit, its edge is smaller than the eye-frontal contact + eye-loreal contact; postnasal irregularly heptagonal, more or less similar in proportion to prenasal, prefrontal-postnasal contact wider than eye-prefrontal contact; loreal moderate, eye-loreal contact less than eye-prefrontal contact and loreal-postnasal contact; eye oval, 0.55-0.81 in males and 0.51-0.56 in females END; two postoculars, first enlarged, second elongated; temporal formula 1+2, supratemporal elongated usually present, first temporal enlarged. Mental subtriangular, wider than

long; six infralabials, three in contact with genials (Fig. 9A₃-B₃); sublabials or pseudo-chinchiels separated from each other, width greater than suture of single pair of infralabials; 3-4 gulars, two prementals; 145-160 ventrals in males (n = 5, = 150.4 ± 5.6391) and 157-170 in females (n = 5, = 154.8 ± 5.5856); cloacal shield entire; subcaudals divided, count in males 27-31 (n = 5, = 28.6 ± 1.5165) and 24-30 (n = 5, = 25.6 ± 2.8809) in females. Thin tail, 9-11.3 % in females and 12.3-14.1 % in males. 17 rows of dorsal scales in the middle of the body, without reduction towards the neck and tail.

Maxillar bone

Arched in lateral view, well-developed lateral process, arranged horizontally to the bone between 5-6 teeth. 6-8 maxillary teeth (n = 5, Fig. 9C-D), but normally six; the first three with a narrow spacing, while the subsequent ones have a spacing that varies between 1½ to 2 times in relation to the previous ones. The last tooth visibly reduced in relation to the previous one. Posterior projection visible.

Hemipenis (everted organs n = 2)

Moderately bilobed, semicapitate, and semicalyculate organ; subcylindrical lobes with a rounded apical edge, differentiated from the capitulum and a third or more of the hemipenial body (Fig. 9E-F). Lobes and capitulum covered with concentrate spinulate calyces; capitular groove undefined on asulcate and sulcate sides of hemipenis; capitulum located just above bifurcation of sulcus spermaticus, slightly shorter than body of the hemipenial body, and shorter in size to lobes. Sulcus spermaticus bifurcated right in the middle portion of the hemipenial body; body hemipenial globular, wider than the capitulum, extensively covered with hooked spines that are more noticeable towards the periphery, while decrease in size towards the border of the sulcus spermaticus and the basal portion.

Information of coloration (in life)

In general, we have detected at least three dorsal patterns, which can be brown, coppery brown and olive-brown, all with the body mostly uniform (Fig. 10A, E) or with small dark spots, circumscribed to the scales and irregularly arranged (Fig. 10B₂, C₂). Head dorsally is uniform, not differentiated of body, but with a lighter snout; supralabials usually pale yellow, weakly pigmented of black (Fig. 10C₁), less common a reddish-yellow hue (Fig. 10B₁); rostral in

frontal view pigmented of olive-brown, coppery brown or light brown. The ventral region of the body with the background pale yellow, pinkish (Fig. 10A) or yellowish-orange (Fig. 10B₂, D), all with dark spots arranged laterally on each ventral scale; cloacal shield immaculate or pigmented of dark brown, subcaudals strongly blemished brown or black; head with the background ventrally cream, pale yellow or yellowish-orange, with the infralabials and genials weakly pigmented black. Pupil dark brown or coppery brown.

Distribution and natural history

Middle-high basin of the Chama River between 1600-2450 m and the upper basin of the Capaz River between 1900-2300 m asl, both regions corresponding to the Sierra de la Culata, Mérida state, Venezuela (Fig. 7). The type locality “Mucurubá” (Esqueda & La Marca 2005) exhibits strong precipitation seasonality (less than 1000 mm year), which is why the natural vegetation corresponds to the montane dry evergreen forest that varies between 2000-2700 m asl. On the other hand, the towns of Mérida and Capaz correspond to the montane Andean semideciduous forest and the cloud forest, respectively (Ataroff & Sarmiento 2004). Although they have not been found together, it is likely that it shares habitat with *A. taphorni* in the upper basin of the Capaz River (MZUC 48034-35 collected 5.84 km NW in cloud forest, LFE 2021).

In Capaz via San Rafael del Macho, 8°39'15.51"N and 71°21'30.28"W, 2031 m asl, 29 specimens were collected (not all yet entered into the Zoology Museum of the University of Concepción, LFE). The site constitutes a fallow land of grasses, ferns, and some trees that seem to be part of the cloud forest. Abrupt terrain and soil with mounds of compacted earth where specimens were found, others by digging or under rocks and accumulated vegetation debris. A few minutes from the site, there was a more or less intact stretch of the

cloud forest, with many rocks; some were lifted, and we found more specimens (field data LFE 2021).

A specimen MCZ R-1784 comes from Mérida, which suggests that the species would be present in the montane Andean semideciduous forest, currently very fragmented. Esqueda & La Marca (2005) noted *A. taphorni* for the city of Mérida, which corroborates the sympatric condition of both species.

Specimens MZUC 45684-85, adult females contained four oviductal eggs, respectively; while MZUC 48687 and MZUC 45686 contained three oviductal eggs.

Conservation status

Due to the number of localities, we did not conduct an ecological niche modeling. However, according to IUCN (<https://geocat.iucnredlist.org/editor>) this taxon would have an EOO of 201.904 km² (extent of occurrence) and an AOO of 12 km² (area of occupancy). Our data indicate that this taxon has disjunct populations, and in these localities, there is a significant conversion of its natural habitat. For example, towards the upper basin of the Capaz River, cloud forest lower montane showed a negative balance, with a net loss of 38.9 % between 1952-1997, replaced by grasslands for high-altitude livestock grazing and agricultural crops (Rodríguez-Morales *et al.* 2009). This conversion pattern is similar for the semideciduous forest and the dry evergreen forest towards the other previously mentioned locations (Buitrago *et al.* 2011). Due to its specialized diet and the direct effects resulting from the dynamics of the original vegetation cover, we believe that this taxon meets the IUCN conservation criteria (IUCN 2012) it must be included in the Vulnerable category according to criteria B2 (i,ii,iii,iv) (see Esqueda & La Marca 2015).

Figure 9. Morphological details related to *Atractus mijaresi*. Specimen MZUC 48032, (A₁) dorsal view of head; (A₂) lateral view of head; ventral view of the and (A₃) frontal view of the frontal scale (A₄). Specimen CVULA 7410, (B₁) dorsal view of head; (B₂) lateral view of head; ventral view of head (B₃), frontal view of the frontal scale (B₄) and lateral view of body (B₅). Specimen CVULA 7410, internal and external view of the maxilla (C). Spécimen MZUC 45678, internal and external view of the maxilla, designated as *A. tamaensis* (D). Specimen MZUC 45679 as *A. mijaresi*, sulcate and asulcate view of hemipenis (E). Specimen MZUC 45680 as *A. mijaresi*, sulcate and asulcate view of hemipenis (F). Specimen MZUC 45678 as *A. tamaensis*, sulcate and asulcate view of hemipenis (G) and Specimen MZUC 45680 as *Atractus* sp., sulcate and asulcate view of hemipenis (H).

Figure 10. Details of the coloration in life of *A. mijaresi*, all the images derive of the material collected in Capaz, Mérida state, Venezuela. Specimen MZUC 48032, uniform brown dorsal pattern and pink belly (A). Specimen MZUC 45682, reddish-brown dorsal pattern, yellowish supralabials, and orange belly (B₁-B₂). Specimen LFE 106, light brown dorsal pattern with small dark spots, pale yellow supralabials, and belly (C₁-C₂). Specimen MZUC 45679, orange ventral surface and strongly dark brown-spotted subcaudals (D). Specimen MZUC 48031, uniform dark brown dorsal pattern (E). Specimen MZUC 45669, dorsal and ventral view of *A. tamaensis* (F). *Atractus* sp., that comes from Las Porqueras and El Triunfo, estado Táchira, Venezuela (G-I). *A. eriki*, that comes from Escuque, Trujillo state, Venezuela por © Santos Bazó (J). *A. mariselae*, uncatalogued, coming from Boconó, Trujillo state, Venezuela por © Luis Felipe Esqueda (K). *A. multidentatus*, holotype CVULA IV-7080 (L) and *Atractus* aff. *pamplonensis*, specimen MCNC 8269 coming from Betania, Táchira state, Venezuela (M).

Atractus* aff. *pamplonensis

Atractus pamplonensis. Schargel & García-Pérez (2002:400)

Atractus pamplonensis. Passos *et al.* (2024:51).

Description on museum material (Venezuela)

Adult female with total length 459.18 mm (SVL = 413.15 mm); tail length 46.03 mm; head length 11.58; head width 6.89 mm. Head in dorsal view: distinctly longer than wide, somewhat differentiated from the neck, weakly compressed (ID/IND relation 34.9 %); snout slightly truncated; rostral slightly visible from above; two internasals, wider than long, internasal suture 0.84 mm (three times prefrontal length); two prefrontals, longer than wide, prefrontal-postnasal contact 0.85 mm, wider than eye-prefrontal contact (0.63 mm); frontal shield longer than wide (3.67 mm and 3.33 mm), anterior edges convex; two supraoculars, elongated and irregularly pentagonal; two parietals, parietal suture 2.97 mm, shorter than FL. Head in lateral view: snout sub-acuminated; eye sub-oval, 1.61 mm (36.1 % less than HED), eye-nostril distance 2.52 mm; prefrontal-eye contact greater or equal than loreal-eye contact; loreal moderate, pentagonal, loreal-postnasal contact similar or greater than loreal-eye contact (2.16 mm LOL, 0.81 mm HLO), in contact with two supralabials; postnasal irregularly heptagonal, higher than wide, similar in size to the prenasal and obliquely arranged, well-defined nostril; two postoculars, the first irregularly pentagonal, longer than wide, wide temporal-1st postocular contact, second postocular small, dorsally in contact with the fifth supralabial and separated from the fourth supralabial; temporal formula 1+2; anterior temporal enlarged; posterior supratemporal elongated not defined (only right side); 7(3,4)/7(3,4) supralabials, first supralabial moderate-enlarged, moderate or ample supralabial-rostral contact; horizontal distance between supralabials in contact with ocular orbit 3.17 (20.5 greater than END). Head in ventral view: subtriangular mental, wider than long; six infralabials, three in contact with genials; a pair of genials, 3.38 mm long (26 % greater than END); two sublabials or pseudo-chinchiels, separated from each other (0.692 mm), just greater than suture of the first pair of infralabials (0.631 mm); three gulars and two preventrals; 178 ventrals; entire cloacal scale, 29/29 subcaudals. Thin tail, 11.1 %. Dorsal scales disposed in 17-17-17 rows.

Coloration of the specimen MCNC 8269 (preservative)

There are no details on the coloration in life. The preserved specimen presents the dorsal background of the body in chocolate brown, with two lines of dark brown spots at the paravertebral level (Fig. 10M₁), then at the dorsolateral level, faintly other rows of irregular dark spots are observed, rows 1-3 dorsal similar to the body, not bordered by cream or yellow. Dorsal background of the head uniform, similar to the dorsal background of the body. At the ventral level, the body background is ochre yellow, heavily mottled with black; generally, the dark brown spots are rectangular, arranged horizontally on each ventral scale and forming two continuous lateroventral lines (between the third and middle of the belly, the spots extend over almost the entire surface of the scale, Fig. 10M₂). Ventral surface of the cloaca weakly mottled with dark brown towards the sides; subcaudals yellow with the same ventral pattern as the body. Head with an ochre yellow background, more subdued, with the mental, infralabials, and genials strongly mottled with dark brown.

Distribution and natural history

Population of Betania, Táchira state, Venezuela (2442 m asl, 7°27' 7"N and 72° 26' 28"W), which corresponds to the Tamá massif. According to this data, this taxon would be occupying the Andean cloud forest. A specimen from the same locality recognized as *A. pamplonensis* was reported by Schargel & García-Pérez (2002).

Table 1. Comparative morphology in the species of *Atractus* from Venezuela (in discussion).

Morphological details, coloration and geographical	<i>A. ventrimaculatus</i>	<i>A. ochrosetrus</i>	<i>A. mijaresi</i>	<i>A. pamplonensis</i>	<i>A. tamaensis</i>	<i>Atractus xaxi</i>	<i>A. mariselae</i>
Geographic distribution in cordillera de Mérida, Venezuela	Restricted to the middle-high basin of the Chama River, Mérida state	Restricted to the middle-upper basin of the Mocoties River, Mérida and Táchira states	It is restricted to the middle-upper basin of the Chama River, towards La Culata (intramontane-lacustrine slope), Mérida state, from Mucurubá, the city of Mérida, and Capaz (upper basin).	So far, two specimens that match the original description and come from Betania, Táchira state have been identified.	type series comes from Betania, Táchira state; new identified populations come from Bailadores (Las Playitas-Las Minas), middle-upper basin of the Mocoties River	Restricted to Jají and its surroundings, Mérida state	Boconó and its surroundings, Trujillo state; the species has not been found towards Niquitao, the outermost part of the Boconó River.
Altitudinal range m asl	1700-3250	2000-3000	1900-2300	1200-2500 in Colombia ***, ~2400 in Venezuela	1900-2000	1800	1200-1300
Type of habitat (natural), according to Ataroff and Sarmiento (2004)	Cloud forest	Cloud forest, elfin cloud forest, Andean montane semideciduous forest	Cloud forest, Andean montane semideciduous forest	Cloud forest	Andean montane semideciduous forest	Andean montane semideciduous forest	Andean montane semideciduous forest
Maximum Total Length (SVL + TaL)	372 mm males and 413 mm females	376 mm males and 421 mm females	348 mm males and 377 mm females	273 mm male in holotype *** and 459 mm female, specimen comes from Betania, Táchira state, Venezuela	283 mm males and 305 mm females	390 mm females ****	325 mm males and 395 mm females ****
Tail with relation SVL	Thick tail, 4.7-8.9 % females and 10.3-15.7 % in males	Thick tail, 6.6-9.1 % in females and 10.6-13.2 % in males	Thin tail, 9-11.3 % in females and 12.3-14.1 % in males	Thin tail, 8.4-12 % in females and 15.5 % in males	Thin tail, 6.6-9.1 % in females and 10.6-13.2 % in males	Thin tail, 11 % in females	Thin tail, 6.6-9.1 % in females and 10.6-13.2 % in males
Wide at the middle of the body (WMB)	> 9 mm	> 9 mm	£ 9 mm	£ 9 mm	£ 9 mm	£ 9 mm	£ 9 mm
Rows of dorsal scales at midbody	15	15	17	17	17	17	17

Ventral scale count	138-153 males and 147-161 females	144-152 males and 146-156 females	145-160 males and 157-170	167-169 males and 174-193 females. In Passos et al. (2024) it is not defined from the examined sample whether the Venezuelan material was included, so we took the averages: 167 in males and 177 in females	145-152 males and 160-165 males ****	168-169 females	168-171 females and 157-162 males ****
Subcaudal scale count	18-22 males, 13-20 females	21-20 males, 14-18 females	27-31 males, 24-30 females	24-35 males and 18-29 females, In Passos et al. (2024): 24-34 males and 19-28 females	26-28 males and 21-23 females ****	28-35 females	31-33 females and 36-39 males ****
Supralabials	Usually 8(4,5)	Usually 8(4,5)	7(3,4)	7(3,4) ***	7(3,4)	8(3,4)	8(3,4), rare seven
Infralabials	7(4)	7(4)	6(3)	7(3-4) ***	6(3)	7(4)	7(4-5)
Sublabials or Pseudo-Chinshields	Separated from each other	Usually in contact	Separated from each other	Separated from each other	Separated from each other	Separated from each other	Separated from each other
Supralabials in contact with Loreal	three, less common two	three, but is frequently specimens with two	two	two	two	three	three, rare two
1st supralabial	Small, short-moderate rostral-supralabial contact	small, short-moderate rostral-supralabial contact	Enlarged, moderate rostral-supralabial contact		Enlarged, moderate rostral-supralabial contact		
Eye-prefrontal contact	> than prefrontal-postnasal contact	> than prefrontal-postnasal contact	< than prefrontal-postnasal contact	< than prefrontal-postnasal contact	< than prefrontal-postnasal contact	< than prefrontal-postnasal contact	< than prefrontal-postnasal contact

Rostral (frontal view)	Subtriangular, usually higher than wide or as high as wide, lateral margins slightly concave or straight, moderate-ample apical margin, situated above the straight line between the nostrils, > 0.5 END	Subtriangular, usually as wide as high or as high as wide, straight, or barely concave lateral margins, short-moderate apical margin, above the straight line between the nostrils, ≤ 0.5 END	Subtrapezoidal, wider than high or as high as wide, concave lateral margins, short apical margin, ≤ 0.5 END, barely crosses the straight line between the nostrils	Scale slightly visible from above. Although we did not have the material to verify its shape in frontal view, it does not suggest that it could be taller than wide, with a moderate apical margin.	Subtrapezoidal, wider than high or as high as wide, concave lateral margins, short apical edge, ≤ 0.5 END, barely crosses the straight line between the nostrils	Subtriangular, as high as wide or slightly higher, straight lateral margins, short-moderate apical edge (<0.5 END), just above the straight line between the nostrils	Subtrapezoidal, wider than high or as high as wide, straight lateral margins, moderate apical edge, ≤ 0.5 END, barely crosses the straight line between the nostrils
Elongated posterior supratemporal	absent	absent	frequently present	variable ***	frequently present	absent	frequently present
First supralabial in contact with the eye	Small, higher than wide; short supralabial-rostral contact	Small, higher than wide; short supralabial-rostral contact	Enlarged, supralabial-rostral contact usually moderate-wide	Enlarged, short supralabial-rostral contact	Small, taller than wide, short supralabial-rostral contact	Small, higher than wide, short supralabial-rostral contact	Small, taller than wide, short supralabial-rostral contact
Suture internasal			Short, three times prefrontal suture; internasals longer than wide	Short, three times prefrontal suture; internasals wider than long	Short, three times suture prefrontal; internasals wider than long, less common quadrangular	Moderate, 2 ½ times prefrontal suture; internasals wider than long	Short, almost three times prefrontal suture; internasals longer than wide
Frontal scute	Usually longer than wide, hexagonal or subhexagonal	Usually as long as wide, subtriangular	Normally as long as wide, hexagonal	Longer than wide, hexagonal, anterior margins convex	Slightly longer than wide or as long as wide, hexagonal, with the anterior margins convex or slightly convex	Hexagonal, wider than long, shorter than the parietal suture and with the anterior margins medially forming a triangle-shaped notch	Longer than wide, subhexagonal, anterior margins slightly convex
Supraocular	Long, subtrapezoidal, posterior edge in parietal contact at least twice as wide as the anterior edge	Long, subtrapezoidal, posterior edge in parietal contact at least twice three times than anterior edge	Short-moderate, usually subtrapezoidal, less common sub rectangular, posterior edge in parietal contact barely 1 ½ times anterior edge	Short-moderate, sub rectangular, posterior edge in parietal contact at least just wider than anterior edge	Short-moderate, usually sub rectangular, less common subtrapezoidal; posterior edge in parietal contact at least just wider than anterior edge	Long, sub rectangular, barely posterior edge in parietal contact wider than anterior edge	Long, subtrapezoidal, posterior edge in parietal contact at least twice than anterior edge

<p>Maxillar and lateral posterior process</p>	<p>Arched, lateral process moderately defined or pronounced, horizontally arranged with respect to the bone, located between the seventh and ninth tooth</p>	<p>Weakly arched, lateral process well-defined, disposed obliquely with respect to the bone, located between the sixth and eighth tooth</p>	<p>Arched and short, well-developed lateral process, arranged horizontally to the bone between 5-6 teeth; defined posterior process</p>	<p>Arched anteriorly in dorsal view, medially flattened toward its posterior end; maxilla with nine teeth arranged linearly; teeth 1-2 larger and little spaced; teeth 3-7 smaller than first teeth, moderately spaced; last two teeth small (holotype) ***</p>	<p>Arched and short, well-defined lateral process, arranged obliquely; defined posterior process</p>	<p>Arched, well developed lateral process, located between the fifth and sixth tooth</p>	<p>Data not available</p>
<p>Maxillary teeth count</p>	<p>10-14 ***, here 11-12, the last one tooth not reduced</p>	<p>8-10, the last one tooth reduced</p>	<p>5-8 maxillary teeth, usually six</p>	<p>frequently 8-9 teeth ***</p>	<p>5-7 teeth</p>	<p>8 teeth</p>	<p>8-9 teeth</p>
<p>Hemipenis</p>	<p>Unilobed, semicapitate, semicalyculate; capitular groove undefined</p>	<p>Unilobed, semicapitate, semicalyculate; capitular groove undefined</p>	<p>Moderately bilobed, semicapitate, semicalyculate; subcylindrical lobules with a rounded apical border; body of the hemipenis globular, extensively longer than lobules; capitular groove not defined in both sides (sulcate-asulcate)</p>	<p>Slightly bilobed, semicapitate, semicalyculate ; clavate lobules with round apices; capitulum extensively wider than body of the hemipenis; capitular groove indistinct on sulcate face, barely defined at asulcate side of organ ***</p>	<p>Poorly defined, semicapitate, semicalyculate ; lobes with straight apices; capitulum wider than body of the hemipenis; capitular groove undefined (asulcate-sulcate)</p>	<p>Information on hemipenis unknown</p>	<p>Slightly bilobed, no capitate, semicalyculate; capitulum no wider than the body of the hemipenis; capitular groove undefined (asulcate-sulcate) ****</p>

<p>Dorsal pattern in life</p>	<p>The most commonly observed pattern is melanic, with or without an undefined vertebral line; another pattern consists of light brown, grayish, or yellowish, with black spots (which may or may not be bordered in yellow), discontinuous and arranged linearly on the body. Another rarely observed pattern is a dark brown background with two narrow yellow lines, paravertebral and partially discontinuous, with no visible black vertebral line.</p>	<p>The pattern often observed has a light brown background, a continuous black vertebral line, and two continuous black lines, narrow or wide (one on each side); another pattern has a similar background but with paravertebral, dorsolateral lines, and a discontinuous narrow vertebral line, with a well-defined cream band between the paravertebral and dorsolateral lines; finally, there are specimens with a melanistic pattern, but the dorsolateral lines are well-defined and bordered with cream. There are individuals that exhibit a yellowish background, with a wide and continuous vertebral line, while the black dorsolateral lines are well-defined and not bordered by cream.</p>	<p>Variable, light brown, grayish brown, or reddish brown, it can be uniform or with small dark spots bordered by the scale and arranged irregularly</p>	<p>Body reddish brown with black marks (dots, spots, or blotches) ***</p>	<p>Light brown or reddish-brown, uniform or with small dark spots arranged regularly over the paravertebral region. These small spots, no larger than a scale, can gradually decrease in size and eventually disappear in some individuals.</p>	<p>Black uniform, no visible stains</p>	<p>Light brown, dark brown, or olive brown; it can be uniform or have small dark spots irregularly dispersed</p>
<p>Ventral pattern in life</p>	<p>Intense yellow background, with blocks of rectangular black spots, some covering the entire scale; pattern normally moderately to heavily spotted</p>	<p>Intense yellow background, with blocks of rectangular black spots, some covering the entire scale; moderately to heavily spotted normal pattern</p>	<p>Pale yellow, pink, or orange background, weakly speckled with black or with rectangular black spots on each side of the ventral scale (its extent does not cover 50% of the surface)</p>	<p>Intense yellow, usually with black spots on each side of the ventral scale (covering more than 50% of the surface)</p>	<p>Pale yellow, usually immaculate, or barely speckled with small black spots on each side of the ventral scale (less than 50 % of the surface)</p>	<p>Whitish, with black spots arranged horizontally on each scale</p>	<p>Whitish or cream, weakly speckled with irregular black or with poorly defined spots arranged horizontally</p>
<p>Ventral surface of the tail</p>	<p>Usually moderately to heavily stained black with a yellow background</p>	<p>Usually immaculate or faintly stained with black and with a yellowish background</p>	<p>Weakly or moderately to strongly stained black with a pale yellow, orange, or pink background</p>	<p>Usually moderately to heavily stained black and with an intense or pale-yellow background</p>	<p>A pale-yellow background, immaculate or faintly stained with black</p>	<p>Moderately to heavily stained black and the background similar to the belly</p>	<p>Usually moderately to heavily stained black and the background similar to the belly</p>

Light band or spot behind the parietals	Absent	Absent	Absent	Incomplete light band and inconspicuous in some adults, juveniles with a band conspicuous	No light band, light spot bordered in black in some adults, more common in juveniles	Absent	Absent
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Data defined by us based on examined material (without asterisk); data defined by Passos *et al.* (2024) (**). Data from other authors (***): Lancini 1969, Esqueda & La Marca 2005, Natera-Mumaw *et al.* 2015

Note: although Passos *et al.* (2024) had a considerable sample of *A. pamplonensis* specimens (Colombia), they mixed the data with Venezuelan specimens, making a coherent analysis impossible. For that reason, it is not considered, except for the average in males and females provided by these authors.

DISCUSSION

Biogeography, species limits and taxonomy

Similar to *Liolaemus* (Esquerré *et al.* 2019), *Atractus* constitutes a lineage that has diversified explosively in the mountains of South America, dominating the middle-high environments between 1000-3200 m asl (e.g., north and central Andes). Serrano *et al.* (2024) proposed that during the Early Miocene, the movement of dipsadines from Central America to South America involved different processes, dating back to approximately 20-25 Myr, whereas the genera *Geophis* + *Atractus* are around 22 Myr, with their Central American ancestors first expanding their distribution to South America and subsequently experiencing vicariance. Our calibrated phylogeny constructed estimated the divergence of *Atractus* with respect other dipsadines around 22.54 Myr (95 % HDP = 19.08-26.23). By way of comparison, the common ancestor of hummingbirds in South America occurred 22 Myr ago, where a substantial proportion of hummingbird diversification took place in conjunction with the uplift of the Andes, around 140 spp., and where Coquettes and Brilliants completed the great majority of their speciation took place over the last 10 Myr in the context of the rapidly rising Andes (McGuire *et al.* 2014).

At that time, the scenario concerning the central and northern Andes was particularly fundamental for understanding the dispersion, colonization, and diversification of these snakes. In fact, the Andean orogeny is considered one of the most important events regarding the diversity of South American biota (e.g., amphibians, Hutter *et al.* 2013). Events to consider in our analysis: (1) during the Miocene, 26-6 Ma, the eastern cordillera began its uplift and the Magdalena River valley formed as a lowland corridor, whose habitat was primarily arid (Egbue & Kellogg 2012), what could have driven the dispersion and colonization in mountain slopes (foothills). During 15.3-23.8 Myr, the transgression of shallow seas into the northern Andes constituted a barrier to the east and a historical connection between the Amazon basin and the Chocó (Hoorn 1994), which must have favored the dispersion between both biogeographic regions. In our phylogeny, with moderate support, we found *A. trilineatus* related to *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. ventrimaculatus*, with a divergence that occurred 17.18 Myr ago, suggesting an ancestor whose dispersion it must have been from the western Amazon basin. On the other hand, although our phylogeny does not encompass 50 % of the known

species, at least three clades (Andean spp. + Andean-Amazonian spp. and Andean-Central American spp.) are visualized with weak support; (2) during most of the early and middle Miocene, the upper Amazon region was covered by the great Pebas wetland (Wesselingh & Salo 2006, Hoorn *et al.* 2010); (3) the role of the Táchira depression as a barrier between the eastern cordillera of Colombia (Magdalena River valley) and the cordillera de Mérida (Andean slope towards Los Llanos and intramontane regions); (4) origin, continuity, and distribution of the cloud forests to the north of the Andes, understanding the dynamics of species between the eastern cordillera of Colombia and the Mérida cordillera. Of the species known in the cordillera de Mérida (Natera-Mumaw *et al.* 2015), *A. ochrosetrus*, *A. ventrimaculatus*, *A. taphorni* and *A. emigdioi* are intramontane species that occupy an altitudinal range comprising the Andean cloud forest between 1800-3000 m (Ataroff & Sarmiento 2004). Species of the Andean cloud forests exhibit a mosaic of evolutionary histories and rapid diversification rates (Pérez-Escobar *et al.* 2023), and many of these radiations occurred from the Early Miocene, when the formation of the cloud forest is believed to have happened (Sempere *et al.* 2005, Bermúdez *et al.* 2011). (5) climatic oscillations during the Pliocene-Pleistocene in the cordillera de Mérida. These climatic fluctuations and the extensive glaciations of the late Pliocene and Pleistocene may have contributed to the expansion and diversification of their distribution area in many organisms through temporary dispersal corridors through suitable habitats, followed by fragmentation into refuges (e.g., birds, Chaves *et al.* 2011) or the contraction of environments at the intramontane level that favored isolation (e.g., mammals, Quiroga-Carmona 2021; plants, Flantua & Hooghiemstra 2018).

Our dating indicates that the divergence of *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. ventrimaculatus* must have occurred at some point during the Late Miocene, coinciding with the uplift of the northern Andes between 8-5 Myr (Pérez-Escobar *et al.* 2022) and in line with what was stated by Boschman (2021), who suggested that the cordillera de Mérida had elevations between 3500-4000 m 7 Myr ago due to the discovery evidences of paramo vegetation in the sediments of the Lake Maracaibo basin, and that other recently described species suggest the same scenery (e.g., *Tantilla palamala*, Esqueda *et al.* 2025a) The cordillera de Mérida is considered a double-vergent orogen with the wetter basin and wedge of the Lake Maracaibo basin on the northwest side and the drier basin and wedge of

Barinas on the southeast side (Erikson *et al.* 2012), creating a pattern determined by its extensive and variable altitudinal gradient and the presence of two different climatic regimes between both slopes, which directly influence the landscapes of the intramontane valleys (Chacón-Moreno & Moral 2020). Hence, *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. ventrimaculatus* are separated by an extensive dry valley known as the González basin, in the middle-lower basin of the Chama River (León 1999). On the other hand, our phylogeny strongly supports that *A. taphorni* and *A. emigdioi* are sister species, whose divergence occurred 3.59 Myr ago (HDP = 1.92-5.47), while *A. mijaresi* and *Atractus* sp. would be related but separated of *A. mariselae*, a species that occupies a lower altitudinal zone (1200-1300 m), although in the same area that *A. emigdioi* (1800-2300 m, LFE data 2021). Passos *et al.* (2024: 81) erroneously consider that both species are very similar, with the possibility that both taxa are conspecific. Furthermore, these authors in their manuscript arbitrarily and without concrete evidence incorrectly use the term “parapatric species” (no phylogenetic evidence to support it). Far from reality, both taxa have distinct histories and absolutely indisputable morphological differences, in addition to relationships with Andean taxa. So far, our data corroborate that the intramontane region of the cordillera de Mérida exhibits the greatest diversification of the genus, strongly related to the Andean uplift and climatic oscillations during the Pliocene-Pleistocene. The cordillera de Mérida is a unique orogen that features an extensive intramontane region, characterized by deep valleys and variations in altitude that act as a geographical barrier, favoring genetic drift and the differentiation of high-montane lineages (e.g., birds in other mountainous regions, Chaves *et al.* 2011). *Atractus* could be a typical example of the “sky island” effect in montane reptiles. Our analyses showed that these two species have very similar and restricted niches, which is consistent with recent speciation influenced by topography and climate. However, despite their phylogenetic divergence, both species have retained their ancestral niche (niche conservatism, Wiens & Graham 2005), possibly due to physiological or ecological constraints. Under this preliminary scenario, it is suggestive to think that these snakes exhibit high speciation rates in mountains and are consistent with the cradle hypothesis, which posits that Andean lineages have higher speciation rates compared to other regions in South America (Esqueda 2005, Esqueda *et al.* 2005b,c).

Despite the accumulated progress in the last 10 years regarding the taxonomy of *Atractus*, we are

far from understanding its diversity and relationships (e.g., only 43 % of the species are available at the phylogenetic level). Although we recognize the contribution of the article by Passos *et al.* (2024), we don't agree with the treatment of the species from the Venezuelan Andes. This reticence has been driven largely by two distinct, interrelated instances: (1) a long-standing disagreement over species concepts, facilitating erroneous and convenient interpretations that do not follow a biogeographic and phylogenetic conceptualization; (2) it is true that many species require an evaluation due to the little that is known, but that does not imply that the current comparisons are based on convoluted criteria, conveniently used for some species and not for others, including incorrect identifications of specimens and/or localities. Therefore, far from resolving the issue, is markedly biased and riddled with inconsistencies that urgently need clarification.

Atractus ochrosetrus vs. *A. ventrimaculatus*: both closely related species diverged in the Late Miocene 6.67 Myr ago (95% HPD = 4.4-9.02). Our combined study data offer an opportunity to examine the importance of these geographic discontinuities and test whether the patterns of intraspecific differentiation are related to differences in niche space (in terms of altitudinal zonation and habitat preference). Both mitochondrial and nuclear DNA data, when comparing both taxa in terms of their patterns of geographic subdivision, degree of genetic differentiation, and inferred demography, consistently demonstrate their taxonomic recognition.

Passos *et al.* (2024: 43) pointed out that Esqueda & La Marca (2005) mistakenly interpreted the condition of the hemipenis of *A. ventrimaculatus*. Is well is true this information, conveniently Passos *et al.* (20024) overlooked what was indicated by Esqueda *et al.* (2007), those who had the opportunity to correct and highlight some distinct attributes of the hemipenes between *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. ventrimaculatus*. In fact, if we review the information on the hemipenis of *A. ventrimaculatus* provided by Passos *et al.* (2024: 42), these authors noted “slightly bilobed, semicapitate, semicalyculate; lobes similar in size, clavate with round apices, weakly distinct from capitulum”, inclusive these authors do not indicate which specimen their description is based on (v. Schargel & Castoe 2003). Our information about the hemipenis of *A. ventrimaculatus* contradicts that indicated by these authors, as we consider that the

hemipenis is unilobed, not clavate, and with rounded edges, with the remaining attributes similar to what was previously known for the species. Although the use of hemipenial characters in systematic studies of *Atractus* has been fundamental and necessarily defined in modern descriptions, if possible (Passos *et al.* 2018), its variability has not yet been fully tested. However, evidence does not suggest that hemipenial morphology in snakes is highly conserved intraspecifically, but it is poorly documented (e.g., *Siphlophis*, Zaher *et al.* 1999; *Oxyrhopus clathratus*, Bernardo *et al.* 2012). In the future, it will be necessary to evaluate more hemipenes of this taxon, but since Passos *et al.* (2024) did not provide an illustration or photograph and Schargel & Castoe (2003) only provided an illustration, we prefer to think that it might have been an error since the hemipenis was not fully expanded or at least, is to have indicated when using instrumentation, if they tried to move it distally during its mounting. Consequently, we recognize that the hemipenis of *A. ventrimaculatus* as unilobed, semicapitate, semicalyculate and capitular groove well-defined. Compared to *A. ochrosetrus*, the ornamentation is generally similar, with some difference in the extension of the capitulum, shorter in *A. ochrosetrus* than in *A. ventrimaculatus*, and the body of the hemipenis wider in *A. ochrosetrus* than in *A. ventrimaculatus*. In our calibrated phylogeny, both species are related to *A. trilineatus*, a species of the cordillera de la Costa, whose divergence occurred 17.18 Myr ago (95 % HDP = 13.61-20.87); while *A. vittatus* + *A. matthewi*, both species of the cordillera de la Costa, Venezuela, diverged from the Andean clade where *A. mijaresi*, and *A. marisela* are found 16.73 Myr ago (95 % HPD = 13.36-20.16). Unlike the Andean species *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. ventrimaculatus*, *A. trilineatus* exhibits a non-capitate and slightly bilobed hemipenis.

The original description of *A. ochrosetrus* consisted of three specimens, one adult male and two juveniles. The juvenile ULABG 3007 presents a coloration without lines on the back, and according to the authors, the “back is dark gray, the belly is light gray, and the tail and throat are washed yellowish”. In contrast, the juvenile specimens examined by us, MHNLS 22669-70, near the type locality of the species, clearly exhibit dorsolateral lines, just like the juvenile MZUC 48020 (Fig. 6E1). Passos *et al.* (2024: Fig. 31E-F) incorrectly indicated the collection locality of the adult female specimen ULAB 2409 as “Betania, state of Táchira, Venezuela,” when in reality it comes from Betania, between El Molino and “La Y,” via Estanques-

Canaguá, 2350 m, Pinto Salinas municipality, Mérida state, collected on April 12, 1989, by Enrique La Marca (LFE was an ad Honorem curator for six years of the collection). The only specimens that come from Betania, Táchira state, correspond to *Dendrosophus pelidna*, collected by Enrique La Marca, Juan Elías García, Abraham Mijares, and Maricela Sosa in 1987. Regarding the status of specimen ULABG 2409, it is located to the southwest of the Las González-Estanques basin, which geographically separates it from the sensu populations of *A. ventrimaculatus*. We prefer to keep its definition on hold due to new data that is being evaluated.

Although Passos *et al.* (2024:43) did not have live specimens to corroborate the coloration pattern in *A. ventrimaculatus* and *A. ochrosetrus*, the authors stated “The color differences between the above species mentioned by Esqueda & La Marca (2005) are the result oversimplification of the polychromatic *A. ventrimaculatus*”. The first mistake is not considering available live photographs of both species (e.g., La Marca & Soriano 2004, Natera-Mumaw *et al.* 2015). Coloration patterns in life are lost during preservation, although sometimes they can be retained through formalin treatment (e.g., specimen MCNC 8269 of *Atractus* aff. *pamplonensis*, Fig. 10M). However, there are taxa that can exhibit melanism in their pattern, such as *A. ventrimaculatus*, and some details like the vertebral line would be undefined (not visible). Until now, the information available on the living *A. ventrimaculatus* does not confirm a wide or narrow black vertebral line on the back of the body, except in some preserved specimens that were examined. In fact, Boulenger in his original description noted “a black vertebral sometimes present”, while in another part of the writing it gives the impression that the common pattern is “olive to blackish brown above, uniform or with dark and light spots”. Also, Roze (1966) noted “gray to grayish-brown above, with a black vertebral line that is often reduced to a series of longitudinal black spots”. Usually, melanism in the context of polymorphism occurs that inhabit highlands reptiles, as seen in other *Atractus* collected such as *A. taphorni* and *A. emigdioi* (both found in the cloud forest). Bogert (1949) suggests that darker individuals warm up more quickly under solar radiation, which increases their thermoregulatory efficiency in cold or humid environments (thermal hypothesis), such as the Andean cloud forests. In our ecological niche models (ENM) for *A. ventrimaculatus* and *A. ochrosetrus*, the variable with the highest

contribution was the precipitation of the wettest quarter and general humidity, associated with the cloud forest in their distributions (Clusella-Trullas *et al.* 2007). So, melanism could represent an adaptive response, facilitated by phenotypic plasticity, the gradient of humidity, and temperature in their habitats (West-Eberhard 2003). If so, it could have been maintained in ancestral populations as an adaptive strategy in high-altitude environments. On the other hand, in *A. ventrimaculatus* climatic oscillations of the Pliocene-Pleistocene (e.g., the Mérida glaciation, Shubert & Clapperton 1990) may have favored melanism due to the contraction and expansion of the cloud forest (v. Hooghiemstra & Van der Hammen 2004), unlike *A. ochrosetrus* which mostly occupies more seasonal environments (Mocoties River basin; León 1999, Rivas *et al.* 2009). Although we found individuals of this taxon with melanism (MZUC 48023, Supp. 1_20), the dorsolateral lines are clearly distinguishable. Therefore, the presence of dorsolateral lines in the dorsal region of the body is a distinguishing attribute between both taxa and not oversimplification of the polychromatic. Although the role of polymorphism as a driver of speciation is an open topic in polymorphic and altimontane species (Gray & McKinnon 2007, Pizzato 2012), the more plausible explanation here is that vicariance facilitated the fragmentation of populations and subsequent differentiation in an ancestral species. Under this geographical scenario where the cordillera de Mérida arose diachronically between both slopes (the lacustrine slope rose faster than the one towards Los Llanos; Audemard 2003, Bermudez *et al.* 2011), as a hypothesis, it is possible that *A. ochrosetrus* constitutes the ancestral species and that *A. ventrimaculatus* could have arisen by budding-off (Coyne & Orr 2004), and subsequently, melanism increased due to the climatic oscillations of the Pliocene-Pleistocene.

Atractus mijaresi vs. *A. pamplonensis*: according to our data, *A. mariselae* diverged from *A. mijaresi* and *Atractus xaxi* during the Late Miocene 8.29 Myr ago (95% HPD = 5.85-11.01), while *A. mijaresi* diverged from *Atractus xaxi* (Esqueda *et al.* 2025b) most likely during the end of the Pliocene and the beginning of the Pleistocene 2.85 Myr ago (95% HPD = 0.87-5.21). Despite the geographical distance and distinctive barriers (e.g., semiarid enclave, Las González basin and Táchira depression), Passos *et al.* (2024) arbitrarily considered that *A. mijaresi* as a synonym of *A. pamplonensis*, despite a clear difference in the count of ventral scales, lacking information on the

hemipenis and coloration in life. Morphologically Passos *et al.* (2009a) relates *A. pamplonensis* with *A. sanctamartae* Dunn, 1946, *A. Macondo* Passos, Lynch & Fernandes, 2009, *A. crassicaudatus* (Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854, *A. nigriventris* Amaral, 1933 and *A. variegatus* Prado, 1942 for having a set of characters, in which it stands out hemipenis with a lateral depression in the lobe apices (curiously not indicated in the description of the hemipenis in Passos *et al.* 2024), capitulum broader than hemipenial body (both characters absent in *A. mijaresi*). Although there is still no molecular information on *A. pamplonensis*, *A. mijaresi* would be related to *Atractus* sp. geographically close (actually in description, Esqueda *et al.* in press), and contrary to the information indicated by Passos *et al.* (2024), our morphological data confirm a set of differences between both taxa (Table 1). On the other hand, populations detected in Táchira state (middle-high basin of the Mocoties River), here for us assigned as *A. tamaensis* and *Atractus* sp. (actually in description by Esqueda and col. in prep.), although they present capitulum broader than hemipenial body, they do not have lateral depression on lobe apices (Fig. 8G-H).

Schargel & García-Pérez (2002) identified a specimen MCNG-R 5877 from Betania, Táchira state, a border locality with Colombia and constituting the Tamá massif as *Atractus pamplonensis*. Neither Passos *et al.* (2024) nor we were able to check that specimen. However, we found a series of specimens in the Natural Sciences Museum of Caracas (MCNC) that we provisionally assigned as *Atractus* aff. *pamplonensis*, and their definitive evaluation will be in another article (Esqueda *et al.* in prep.). However, here we describe specimen MCNC 8269 for comparative purposes with the information provided by Schargel & García-Pérez (2002). Although both records share attributes with the information on *A. pamplonensis* provided by Passos *et al.* (2024), these authors point out another population in Colombia as *Atractus* aff. *pamplonensis* (MHUA-R 4867), whose hemipenial morphology can be very different from that defined for *A. pamplonensis* (v. Fig 45A and B, p. 55). Although this hemipenis is stained red, there is an extraordinary similarity with the hemipenis of *A. paisa* (Passos *et al.* 2009c: Fig. 2B, p. 428). On the other hand, there are several strange entanglements in that description that warrant discussion: the description is based on a series of specimens, but upon observing and comparing figure 4 (MHUA 14274) and figure 5 (MHUA 14236), they are actually two distinct species. The first specimen

presents a completely dark uniform coloration and comes from a locality in the central cordillera of Colombia (eastern slope, Magdalena basin), about 312 km in a straight line from the type locality of *A. pamplonensis*, which would be in the Oriental cordillera (western slope). Although Passos *et al.* (2009c) indicated that *A. paisa* would have 17 vs. 15 in *A. lasallei*, it is necessary to reevaluate its status. In fact, the holotype assigned to *A. paisa* Passos, Arredondo, Fernandes & Lynch, 2009 is ICN 10698, but in its description, there is information about the coloration in life that corresponds to the specimen MHUA 14236 (Fig. 5, p. 430). Although the authors illustrate the holotype (Fig. 6, p. 431), the provided lateral view very similar to the paratype MHUA 14274. In the same article, there is another error in the character state when describing *A. titanicus* Passos, Arredondo, Fernandes & Lynch, 2009, where the holotype (Fig. 7, p. 432) clearly has a uniform dorsal coloration, while the specimen ICN 10697 has a banded dorsal pattern (Fig. 8, p. 432), but curiously in their species definition is indicate “banded color pattern, with alternate dark and light dorsal rings (three scales wide)”.

If we examine Passos *et al.* (2024) article on the *Atractus* species of the Venezuelan Andes in detail, we find an evident bias in the information, leading to inconsistent, inaccurate, or subtly omitted data. As an example, we have: (1) the comparison of *A. erythromelas* and *A. meridensis*, where the latter exhibits a set of distinctive morphological characters that were subsequently reevaluated by Esqueda *et al.* (2025c). In their redescription of *A. meridensis*, they noted specimens with duplicate museum numbers, which are corrected here (MZUC 45657 = MZUC 41273; MZUC 45658 = MZUC 41274; MZUC 45659 = MZUC 41275; MZUC 45660 = MZUC 41276); (2) although based on limited information, Passos *et al.* (2024) consider *A. mariselae* to be a synonym of *A. emigdioi*, which is far from the truth, and such assertions are inconsistent with the principles of scientific ethics (Esqueda *et al.* in prep.). We understand the points of view, but never by trying to manipulate the information to fit certain interpretations. In fact, the two species are not phylogenetically related (Esqueda *et al.* 2025b) and exhibit a set of distinctive characters (e.g., head shape and extent, sublabial or postgenials contact, coloration pattern, hemipenes, and maxillary teeth). In contrast, *A. mariselae* is a species with a distribution strictly confined to the Boconó River valley, and its characteristics more closely resemble those of the species group that includes *A. eriki*, *A. mijaresi*, *A.*

tamaensis, and *A. xaxi*. On the other hand, Passos *et al.* (2024) considered *A. eriki* to be a synonym of *A. indistinctus*, a species from east of the Magdalena River in the Eastern cordillera of Colombia, and that it would be more closely related to other species from the serranía de Perijá (e.g., *A. pearti*). These authors included a dubious record of a specimen from the Serranía de Perijá on the Venezuelan side that would have the *A. eriki* pattern; in particular, that specimen lacks a museum number and its characteristics were not discussed, although they are clearly distinct from *A. indistinctus*. Even when comparing *A. turikensis*, the authors noted that the species could be a synonym of *A. indistinctus*, with the aim of complicating the discussion regarding the validity and relationships of *A. pearti*, a species they had described (Esqueda *et al.* in prep.).

Conservation status

Our accumulated field data over several years tell us that the sleepyhead snakes of the cordillera de Mérida tend to be locally common and gregarious in response to a variety of signals such as reproductive or thermal (Aubret & Shine 2009), but with a reduced habitat breadth (< 20,000 km²) and frequently occurs in highlands (Böhm *et al.* 2017), such as other Neotropical snakes (e.g., viperids; Birskis-Barros *et al.* 2019). Until now, all environments above 1500 meters in altitude in the cordillera de Mérida have been seriously affected by anthropogenic activities (Ataroff & Rada 2000, Llambí 2015, Chacón-Moreno *et al.* 2021).

If we invoke the optimal foraging theory (Perry & Pianka 1997), it is possible to think that the spatial and temporal dimension of habitat disturbance could affect specialist reptiles like vermivorous snakes, but there are no studies demonstrating this in *Atractus*. Balestrin *et al.* (2007) are of the opinion that the abundance of *A. reticulatus* in anthromes is due to the adaptation to new prey (introduced earthworms). We are aware that there are more questions than answers, but it is well known that twenty percent of Neotropical reptile species are threatened, with the same proportion catalogued as Data Deficient (Böhm *et al.* 2013). In fact, earthworms are considered ecosystem engineers, have been part of ecosystems for over 400 million years (Maggi & Tang 2021). In this sense, climate change, particularly extremes of drought and flooding, has been shown to directly affect earthworm communities by altering their activity, abundance, and biomass. In addition, the indirect effects of anthropogenic activities on these communities remain poorly studied. Then said

activities, which often result in soil contamination, also negatively affect epigeal biota (Migliani *et al.* 2019, Singh *et al.* 2019), potentially affecting the abundance and distribution of *Atractus* in mountains where preexisting barriers are limiting.

In light of new evidence, we can conclude that *A. ochrosetrus* and *A. mijaresi* are valid species, that exhibit an allopatric and highly fragmented distribution due to the gradual deterioration of their environments; and although are locally abundant, they exhibit a narrow breadth. Therefore, the recognition according to IUCN criteria as Vulnerable provides a solid foundation necessary to reevaluate the biodiversity and conservation status of Andean reptiles. Although the Andes of Venezuela is among the five critical hotspots (Myers *et al.* 2000), the political-social crisis of recent decades has decimated any efforts in that direction (see De Sousa 2023). In fact, if we consider that Oliveira-Miranda *et al.* (2010) published information regarding the vulnerability situation of the ecosystems in the country and that we are unaware of the effect of the crisis due to lack of data (e.g., extraction of wood on Andean forests), the current outlook could be concerning for many reptile species, in particular specialist those like *Atractus* (e.g., *Urotheca multilineata*, Esqueda *et al.* in prep.).

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Data availability

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article (v. supplementary information files in format xlsx, except unpublished data that are not yet public until the time of their publication in the repository GENBANK). All unpublished specimens are not listed on the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species Index and met the standards required by the Ministerio de Ecosocialismo y Aguas (MINEC-Venezuela) under N° DGBD/2021/0095 to Luis

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Supplementary materials

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